

Large-Scale Research Infrastructure

National Roadmap consortia 2024

1. General information

Grant application title: **macroscope**

Consortium lead and other consortium partners

<i>Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) – Lead</i>	<i>KNAW-Huygens Institute (HuC)</i>	<i>Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL)</i>
<i>Centerdata (Centerdata)</i>	<i>KNAW-International Institute of Social History (HuC)</i>	<i>Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen (RU)</i>
<i>Centraal Planbureau (CPB)</i>	<i>KNAW-Meertens Instituut (HuC)</i>	<i>Rijksuniversiteit Groningen (RUG)</i>
<i>Beeld en Geluid (NISV)</i>	<i>Netherlands eScience Centre (eScience Center)</i>	<i>Sociaal en Cultureel Planbureau (SCP)</i>
<i>Delft University of Technology (TUD)</i>	<i>Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI)</i>	<i>Statistics Netherlands (CBS)</i>
<i>Instituut voor de Nederlandse Taal (INT)</i>	<i>Nederlands Studiecentrum Criminaliteit en Rechtshandhaving (NCSR)</i>	<i>Tilburg University (TiU)</i>
<i>Koninklijke Bibliotheek (KB)</i>	<i>Open Universiteit (OU)</i>	<i>Universiteit Leiden - CL (UL)</i>
<i>KNAW-Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)</i>		<i>Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA)</i>
		<i>Utrecht Universiteit (UU)</i>
		<i>VU Amsterdam - FW (VU)</i>

Main applicant

Name	Dr. Tom Emery
Address for correspondence	Burgemeester Oudlaan 50, 3062 PA Rotterdam
Email	tom@odissei-data.nl
Phone number	010 408 1111
Website	www.odissei-data.nl

Consortium ¹	Affil.	Expertise	ORCID	Role(s)
Main applicant				
Dr. Tom Emery	EUR	Sociology	0000-0001-6137-9577	PI
Co-applicant(s)				
Prof. dr. Susan Aasman	RUG	Digital Humanities	0000-0003-1675-2998	Co-PI
Prof. dr. Daniel Oberski	UU	Methodology	0000-0001-7467-2297	Co-PI
Prof. dr. Jacco van Ossenbruggen	VU	Data Science	0000-0002-7748-4715	Tech Lead
Dr. Richard Zijdeman	HuC	Data Science	0000-0003-3902-3720	Tech Lead
Dr. Ricarda Braukmann	DANS	Data Archiving	0000-0001-6383-7148	Task Lead
Ran van den Boom	CBS	Administrative Data	NA	CBS Lead
Prof. dr. Theo Araujo	UvA	Communication Science	0000-0002-4633-9339	Task Lead
Prof. dr. Gijsbert Rutten	UL	Sociolinguistics	0000-0002-6105-8949	Task Lead
Prof. dr. Jessica Piotrowski	UvA	Communication Science	0000-0002-2756-5197	Task Lead

¹ Several members of the consortium only provide co-financing as ODISSEI members, do not execute work and are omitted from this table.

Dr. Laura Boeschoeten	UU	Data Science	0000-0002-3536-0474	Task Lead
Dr. Colette Bos	NLeSC	Data Science	0009-0007-2662-7468	NLeSC Lead
Dr. Henk van den Heuvel	RU	Linguistics	0000-0003-2064-0630	RU Lead

Co-funders

Prof. dr. Marcel Das	Centerdata	Methodology	0000-0002-9895-2776	Task Lead
Dr. Roeland Ordelman	NISV	Technology	0000-0001-9229-0006	Tech lead
Dr. Sophie Ham	KB	Digital Collections	0009-0009-0170-5364	Task Lead
Dr. Jesse de Does	INT	Linguistics	0000-0003-0170-8943	INT Lead

Cooperation Partners

Dr. Matthieu Laneuville	SURF	Machine Learning	0000-0001-6022-0046	Tech Lead
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Relevant research field(s)

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30.30.00	30.55.00	31.90.00	32.70.00	35.40.00	37.30.00	37.90.00	40.40.00	44.20.00	48.90.00
30.40.00	30.90.00	32.20.00	32.80.00	37.10.00	37.40.00	38.10.00	40.50.00	45.90.00	49.11.00

Abstract

In this project we will construct a population level *Macroscopic*, building on existing infrastructures and services from ODISSEI and CLARIAH to deliver unique opportunities for Social Science and Humanities scholars. A Macroscopic is an instrument for the holistic study of complex social dynamics and the Dutch Macroscopic will consist of four complementary and mutually reinforcing layers that support different phases of the research lifecycle in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). First, the **Macroscopic Core** will adapt foundational infrastructures to accommodate the complex, sensitive, and highly interrelated data found across the SSH domain. Second, the **Data Harvesting Ecosystem** will enable unprecedented levels of data variety. Through integrated data systems, new technologies, and intensive collaboration, it will be possible to collect diachronic, dynamic, population data scale, network data on a plethora of social issues. Third, the **AI Collaboratory** will provide a community-oriented platform for the training and evaluation of complex models and tools including a next generation of secure Large Language Models with a vast array of applications for research. Fourth, the **Macroscopic Gateway** will enable scholars from across the domain and beyond to utilise the Macroscopic. Once completed in 2030, SSH researchers will be able to securely bring together an unprecedented range of data, tools, and computational resources to answer societal questions that cannot be addressed presently and conduct groundbreaking multi-disciplinary research into multi-scale, complex social dynamics such as how the Dutch language is evolving in a multimedia world or how demographic change is shifting the social fabric of the Netherlands.

Popular project title and public summary

NL – De Macroscopic

Dit project zal de eerste "Macroscopic" ter wereld creëren, een krachtig hulpmiddel om complexe maatschappelijke problemen op grote schaal te onderzoeken. Door voort te bouwen op bestaande Nederlandse infrastructures zoals ODISSEI en CLARIAH zal de Macroscopic onderzoekers in staat stellen om op een veilige manier toegang te krijgen tot grote hoeveelheden gevoelige, onderling verbonden data en deze te analyseren. De Macroscopic omvat geavanceerde systemen voor dataverzameling, AI-tools en een platform voor samenwerking. Deze innovatieve faciliteit zal het mogelijk maken om onderzoek naar sociale en culturele dynamieken uit te voeren dat nodig is om urgente maatschappelijke vraagstukken aan te pakken.

ENG – The Macroscopic

This project aims to create the world's first "Macroscopic", a powerful tool for investigating complex societal issues at scale. Building on existing Dutch infrastructures such as ODISSEI (for the Social Sciences) and CLARIAH (for the Humanities), the

Macroscope will enable researchers to securely access and analyse large amounts of sensitive, interconnected data. It will include advanced data collection systems, AI tools, and a platform for collaboration. This innovative facility, expected to be completed in 2030, will enable groundbreaking research in the Social Sciences and Humanities, making it easier to investigate complex social dynamics and answer critical societal questions.

2. Large-Scale Research Infrastructure (LSRI)

2.1 General description of the LSRI

When is the next stock market crash? How will the Dutch language be influenced by the increasing internationalisation of higher education? How will climate change reshape cultural narratives in literature and film? Which political parties will be popular in ten years? The answers to such questions are firmly located within the realm of the Social Sciences and Humanities. Yet, in practice, they remain lost in the realm of speculation by media pundits, who do little better than chance¹. Furthermore, even though our data access and computing power are growing tremendously, our ability to predict important social outcomes has not improved.²

This fundamental unpredictability of social phenomena has an explanation: social events are macro-level, emergent characteristics of a complex system³. They are as unpredictable as the next whirl in a turbulent fluid, or the next turn taken by a murmuration of starlings in flight – macro- and meso- level processes that result from a large number of micro-level, individual interactions. But unpredictable does not mean incomprehensible: flocks of starlings have adapted to avoid predators, and aeroplane wings are designed to reduce turbulence, thanks to our understanding of the underlying complex dynamics. Can we do the same through a better understanding of complex societal dynamics?

The Social Sciences and Humanities are about interactions between people and the culture that emanates from them, but empirical research is too often limited to studying individuals in isolation, divorced from their social interactions. This is largely out of necessity, as measuring social interactions is sensitive, complicated, and difficult to do at scale. To improve social outcomes, we therefore need to understand the underlying complex dynamics; and to achieve that, we need an instrument capable of measuring complex interactions at population scale. We then would be better equipped to understand how the enormously varied interactions and characteristics of people coalesce to macro-level behaviour.⁴

Answering this question would constitute a very significant scientific breakthrough. Granted, because such events are fundamentally unpredictable, we still could not say when the next stock market crash will be. Instead, we could design a better stock market with early warning systems for instability and first-rate automated circuit breakers, which is ultimately less prone to crashes. We could develop a social support system that reduces extreme poverty in developed societies by reinforcing and leveraging local support and opportunity networks. We could describe a resilient and transmedial dynamic of public opinion that is less prone to external manipulation, identifying bots, and deploying interventions that strongly disincentive disinformation. This understanding of complex social dynamics is the specific task for which Joël De Rosnay introduced his concept of a “macroscope” in 1979⁴.

What is the Macroscope?

The concept of the “macroscope” was introduced by De Rosnay as an instrument to study the complex systems that envelop us⁵. A macroscope has three characteristics. First, it must take account of the highly varied and **diverse interdependencies and network ties** that exist between people, rather than study individuals in isolation or only one aspect of their interactions. Second, because we, the study subjects, are ourselves inside the complex systems we study, it needs to allow us to “zoom out” to the **population scale**, rather than observing just individual instances of social behaviour. Third, in order to ultimately support better decision-making, it must allow us to study **dynamics**; that is, a macroscope needs to observe these interdependencies and network ties over time. By combining simple computational models of individual interactions with whole-population, networked, diachronic, empirical data, the Macroscope empowers Social Science and Humanities scholars to understand how social dynamics play out in real time, and supports the design of better social policies.

Researchers are well aware of the networked, dynamic nature of social relations. In 2019, a population scale network which represented each individual within the Dutch population in a large, dynamic, multi-layered graph was generated⁶. It linked all 17.8 million inhabitants of the Netherlands with all the neighbours, colleagues, family, and household members resulting in 1.4 billion connections. This graph was then extended over a ten-year period so that relationships are shown to be created, broken, and changed. In the following years, this graph has been extended and used in multiple ways to include different types of relationships⁶, to understand social segregation⁷, and to monitor the spread of COVID⁸.

Similarly, in the Humanities, studies have started enriching the traditional micro-level “close reading” of texts and media with novel macro-level “distant reading” enabled by advances in text mining, natural language processing, and visualisation

techniques⁹, allowing the researcher to “zoom” in and out, as in a macroscope. So far, there have been subject specific implementations such as the innovative OldBaileyVoices project, but there has been no comprehensive implementation of the macroscope concept anywhere in the world – simply because population scale, networked, diverse, dynamic data have not been available anywhere. In the Netherlands, however, the investments of ODISEI and CLARIAH have recently brought such empirical foundations within scope – and the Macroscope within reach. In line with the 2021 National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Facilities, the current proposal will now realise a comprehensive implementation of a “macroscope” – built upon the foundations laid by ODISEI and CLARIAH, and support its general usage throughout the scientific community in the Netherlands and beyond. The Macroscope will enable countless complex research **workflows** consisting of the integrated usage of its various layers. Examples of such workflows are represented in Section 2.2 and Section 5.

Realising the Macroscope

The Macroscope is a “**Platform-as-a-Service**” that consists of four layers and operates as a single technology stack specified in detail in Section 5.

1. Macroscope Core

First, the **Macroscope Core** provides the flexible compute, storage, and archiving that support the onward services in the Macroscope. These facilities are generally available but need to be adapted to support federated storage and retrieval of complex, diverse, dynamic population scale data. It is not possible or desirable to centralise the data used in the Macroscope and it is therefore dependent on a seamless federated architecture. Central to its Core is a Knowledge Graph which acts as the central ‘domain logic’ component of the Macroscope. This Knowledge Graph draws on existing established standards to represent the data, variables, code lists, code, tools, analytical environments, individuals, organisations, publications, and projects in the Macroscope ecosystem, modelling dependencies and managing API (Application Programming Interfaces) calls and complex workflows.

The Macroscope Core consists of:

- Machine-actionable access and authentication through a Data Access Broker (Task 1.1);
- Integrated data discovery of metadata records from various data providers that cover survey data, administrative data, media, and web data including text, image, and audiovisual data from both traditional and online sources (Task 1.1);
- Macroscope Knowledge Graph used to customise and improve machine actionable interoperability (Task 1.1);
- Automated pipelines for spinning up secure container environments regulated by the Data Access Broker (Task 1.2);
- Adaptation of existing secure environments to support federated learning and fine-tuning across distributed data providers (Task 1.2);
- Creation of a general secure supercomputing environment compliant with established security standards (Task 1.2);
- Ingestion of machine-readable variable-level metadata from Statistics Netherlands (Task 1.3);
- Automated output checking for disclosure control, and advanced evaluation algorithms for evidence-based computational workflows (Task 1.3);
- Sampling algorithms to facilitate the use of the Macroscope Core for onward data collection (Task 1.3).

2. Data Harvesting Ecosystem

Second, we will create a **Data Harvesting Ecosystem** that allows researchers to collect data on societal dynamics at multiple scales simultaneously in a globally unique data ecosystem, encompassing linked survey and administrative data from the social sciences and multimedia data from the humanities. It will allow researchers from across the ODISEI and CLARIAH communities to deploy the next generation of sophisticated data collection tools such as Port¹⁰, 4CAT¹¹, and MOE¹². These data collection tools can be used to collect modern relational and complex data structures from a range of sources including the Population Scale Network of the Netherlands, the LISS panel, alignment with a national Microtasking Platform, and secure API connections to cultural heritage repositories. The Ecosystem will create the National Media Corpus which integrates a wide range of media data in a single framework, coordinated by UvA and the National Library of the Netherlands (KB). This will allow not only “close reading” of specific media via research environments, but also “distant reading” based on data enrichment and quantitative analysis techniques, thus covering a diachronic population of study objects.

The Data Harvesting Ecosystem consists of:

- Deployable, enhanced data donation tools in large-scale, nationally representative surveys (Task 2.1);
- Adapting sampling pipelines for large-scale data collections to improve coverage of hard-to-reach groups and other specific populations of interest (Task 2.1);
- Substantially increasing the speed of deployment and reducing costs in large-scale social surveys (Task 2.1);

- Providing researchers with an easy-to-use user interface for designing and deploying modules and experiments in a large-scale, open, representative online probability panel (Task 2.2);
- Testing and evaluating novel sampling algorithms for cost, sustainability, and viability (Task 2.2);
- Integrating a Microtasking Platform for social science and humanities researchers, dedicated to empowering Dutch-speaking participants and citizen scientists (Task 2.2);
- Creating the Netherlands Media Corpus which brings together text, image, and audio-visual data, both traditional and from online sources in a singular framework to support transmedial research (Task 2.3);
- Providing seed grants and support for the upgrade and maintenance of existing data extraction and documentation tools (Task 2.3);
- Supporting transmedial research by creating a representative dataset of thousands of individuals and the media and web “diets” they consume (Task 2.3).

Data in the Macroscopic	
<u>Surveys & Administrative Data</u>	<u>Netherlands Media Corpus</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ The LISS panel (Centerdata)■ Microtasking Platform (Centerdata)■ Administrative Microdata (CBS)■ Population Scale Network (CBS)■ SHARE, ESS, DPES, EVS, ISSP (UU)■ Media Diets Observatory (UvA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Historical and Contemporary Newspapers (KB)■ Web-Archive (KB)■ Historical Correspondence (Huygens)■ Public Television & Radio (NISV)■ Program Guides & Podcasts (NISV)■ Social Media & Data Donation (UvA)

3. AI Collaboratory

Third, we will establish the **AI Collaboratory**. In ODISSEI and CLARIAH, the alignment between exceptionally diverse and linked data and secure computing facilities has allowed researchers to train graph neural networks, Large Language Models (LLMs), and graph-augmented models using data that is only accessible to the research community under strict security conditions.¹³ ODISSEI is the only facility in the world that allows for the training on sensitive microlevel administrative data using a supercomputer. In CLARIAH, the development of the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE), connected to supercomputer facilities and federated modelling approaches, provides a potential framework for researchers to fine-tune existing LLMs such as **GPT-NL** on vast, culturally rich corpora that are outside of the public domain but are of huge scientific value. These proof-of-concept applications have demonstrated significant potential, but considerable investment is needed to ensure that these applications can be scaled technically, securely, and ethically. To achieve this, the AI Collaboratory will provide high-quality, transparent, sustainable tools that support collaboration using a wide range of tasks within Macroscopic workflows.

The AI Collaboratory consists of:

- Fine-tuned LLMs such as GPT-NL and making these queryable via a low-code workflow through which researchers can import their own data and deploy their own tasks (Task 3.1);
- Pipelines that support standardised Retrieval-Augmented Generation workflows deployable through an accessible graphic user interface (Task 3.1);
- Analytical dashboards for evaluating and interacting with federated collections of textual corpora (Task 3.1);
- Development and testing of advanced, automated annotation tools that are interoperable with federated secure environments and complex, multimedia data (Task 3.2);
- Adapted tools and algorithms for large-scale graph analysis that support effective and efficient onward usage of graph data in research (Task 3.2);
- Quality control and tool evaluation that is accessible and easy to interpret by researchers and supported through extensive documentation of tooling (Task 3.2);
- Development of new tools and software modules incorporating new AI technologies, such as intelligent agents that can be used in experiments and secure federated annotation, in large scale data collections (Task 3.3);
- Creation of an open-source platform for hosting and maintaining microtools and software modules that are machine-actionable and ready for deployment in the Macroscopic (Task 3.3);
- Support and seed funding for deployment of tools in combination with the Data Harvesting Ecosystem (Task 3.3).

4. Macroscopic Gateway

Fourth and finally, the **Macroscope Gateway** will provide entry level, introductory access to the Macroscope to researchers from across the country through a Graphical User Interface (GUI). The Macroscope is sophisticated and complex to use. Researchers must master not only substantive material but also an eclectic range of technical skills just to leverage the functionalities of the infrastructure. The Macroscope will provide easy access to simplified, commonly used components. Users will be able to execute simple research workflows without the need to write code, giving them insights and inspiration about how the Macroscope might be used. This will be achieved by providing standardised introductory level walkthroughs which bring together interoperable digital resources from across the Macroscope. Metadata for these digital resources that has been enriched in the Macroscope Knowledge Graph, including evaluation and provenance criteria generated by the other layers of the Macroscope, leverages a domain knowledge component to realise the interoperability needed for the GUI and orchestration. As with any user interface, there is a trade-off between ease-of-use and analytical power; we offer different entry points to different users along this continuum so that more advanced users wanting to go beyond the functionality of the Macroscope GUI receive personalised support from data scientists and research engineers. This technical support will be reinforced with support for Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) that are plentiful in the rapidly evolving fields of computational social science and digital humanities.

The Macroscope Gateway consists of:

- An integrated and user-friendly GUI that is tested on and accessible to the Social Science and Humanities community at large (Task 4.1);
- A domain logic component that draws from the Macroscope Knowledge Graph to orchestrate other components (Task 4.1);
- Dedicated human support from user liaisons who guide researchers through the functionality and standard workflows of the Macroscope and ELSI (Task 4.1);
- A coordinating team that supports the integration of the various Macroscope components and their interoperability (Task 4.1);
- An Ethics forum to support the Ethics Review Boards at ODISSEI and CLARIAH member organisations who are utilising the Macroscope's novel functionalities for research (Task 4.2);
- A Legal team to coordinate legal guidance and compliance across the Macroscope and align the requirements of data holders and service providers in a changing legal framework (Task 4.2);
- Public engagement activities to support a better public understanding of Computational Social Science and Digital Humanities research using the Macroscope (Task 4.2);
- Access to trained and fully funded data scientists to support researchers in using new methods in their own research (Task 4.2);
- Workshops, seminars, and summer schools to support in-person training on new methods and technologies, including excellent training materials and detailed walkthroughs of standard Macroscope workflows (Task 4.2);
- A federated network of data scientists and methodological experts across ODISSEI and CLARIAH member organisations that are indexed and available to the research community (Task 4.2).

2.2 Expected scientific innovation and breakthroughs

The four Macroscope layers – Core, Data Harvesting Ecosystem, AI Collaboratory, and Gateway – are mutually reinforcing. A solid empirical base and secure data access allow for targeted and highly sophisticated data collection strategies; a functional Data Harvesting Ecosystem platform unlocks more sophisticated AI applications; new AI applications can be used to develop refreshing insights for users to explore via the Gateway; and the Gateway itself will bring novice scholars in touch with the latest tools and technologies and maximising impact. Together these will bring groundbreaking technologies to the fingertips of the next generation of researchers across the ODISSEI and CLARIAH communities. Here we offer just five examples of cutting-edge workflows that the Macroscope will enable for researchers in the Netherlands in the next decade.

Example 1: Observing social contagions at population scale

Despite its innovative approach and rich data, the Dutch Population Scale network¹⁴ has notable limitations. The node and edge features included in the graph are all captured via administrative data. They are the footprints we leave when we interact with the state, capture only a fragment of the social world in which we live, and are known to carry specific biases.^{15,16} They do not carry information about many important phenomena of social-scientific interest, such as beliefs, attitudes, religion, skills, housing market behaviour, or voting, for example. To study such phenomena, Social Scientists and Humanities scholars are currently limited to theoretical models, aggregate empirical data, or small-scale networks such as school classes. The Macroscope will pioneer the use of population scale, dynamic network data in the design of sampling algorithms (Task 1.3), which could be used to draw samples and request informed consent for linkage back to the population-scale network (Task 2.2), subject to validation and approval by Centerdata and Statistics Netherlands. Researchers will not only be able to examine individual knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours but also how these features propagate

through the, now known, network of respondents (Task 3.3). For example, it would be possible to study how institutional trust and distrust spread from person-to-person and the extent to which these follow models of complex contagions¹⁷. This is something that is not possible in any other social science infrastructure in the world.

Eszter Bokányi, Post-Doc, Leiden University

“The Netherlands provides opportunities for studying population scale networks that are unparalleled elsewhere in the world. The Macroscopic will provide tools to work with this exceptionally complex and rich data source and elevate our understanding of these population structures and dynamics to new levels.”

Example 2: Simulating market dynamics

The ability to deploy experiments and collect data in which individual respondents are no longer taken to be statistically independent will drastically improve the performance of computational models of social dynamics. Existing agent based models of market dynamics and career trajectories still for the most part operate on the assumption – inherent in traditional source data – that individual records are independent³. While Social Scientists are of course acutely aware that this assumption does not hold in practice, the realities of quantitative social data collection of the past 190 years have necessitated it. So, the data that these models are trained on are unaware of the various relations between individual observations. By drawing on data collected through the Macroscopic’s Data Harvesting Ecosystem (Task 2.1), models can be trained on social data of unprecedented variety, veracity, and volume with interactions between individuals taken to be context dependent. Approaches such as Generative Agent Based Models and Graph Augmented Models are well suited for understanding the complex dependencies in such data and potentially predicting social dynamics far more accurately than the current state of the art (Task 3.2). Such graph based approaches could help us improve modelling and test these models through large-scale simulations in Secure HPC environments (Task 1.2). These approaches are capable of providing a deep empirical base to pre-existing agent based modelling approaches, supporting computationally intensive but informative simulations of societally crucial outcomes. For example, they will help improve our modelling of the housing market and associated outcomes by incorporating the behaviour of neighbours, family members, and employers through the dynamic network data of the Macroscopic. This will help us to understand the interplay between demographic and labour market developments that result in surges in house prices in specific neighbourhoods.

Clementine Cottineau, Assistant Professor, TU Delft

“Generative agent-based models with stochastic and non-linear elements produce large amounts of data because we need to explore both their parameter and output spaces. Empirical agent-based models in Social Sciences require access to socioeconomic microdata for initialising and evaluating the model in a high performance computing environment. The Macroscopic will provide that.”

Example 3: Real-world social dynamics through experimental designs

Researchers who study media corpora are highly reliant on poor quality annotation platforms such as MTurk or Prolific¹⁸. These are of demonstrated low quality, have weak pools of Dutch native speakers, and—crucially— the amount of auxiliary data on research subjects is limited. The Macroscopic will support microtasking and online panel infrastructures that allow for specific subpopulations to annotate specified digital objects such as images or videos with keywords, observations, or opinions (Task 2.2). This Microtasking Platform enables citizen science at scale, by turning research subjects into research participants. Furthermore, the Macroscopic will allow for these participants to be allocated to specific positions within experiments, economic games, and microtasks. Researchers will be able to cross treatment assignment with variables generated using advanced AI tools developed for the Macroscopic’s Data Ecosystem (Task 3.3). This allows Social Scientists and Humanities scholars to understand how social contexts influence an individual’s behaviour within an experiment. If groups of three participants are, for instance, asked to collaboratively annotate the veracity of social media posts, do we see different results if the participants are from the same backgrounds as compared to different ones? Understanding how social context changes an experimental effect is vital for translating experimental inferences to real-world social dynamics and contexts¹². Directly observing social context will facilitate the operationalisation of “actor-network theory”, in which social interactions are mediated by objects. For example, a social historian will easily be able to recruit a large and diverse pool of participants to manually transcribe historical records, sociolinguists can pay participants or reward students for manually coding social media posts, and experimental economists may deploy complex games with a high-quality pool of participants. Such experiments are vital in understanding how knowledge and facts are established and perpetuated throughout groups,

and there is currently no suitable infrastructure in the Netherlands that enables this. The Macroscopic will thus support completely new innovative research lines in experimental humanities and communication science.

Ana Macanović, Post-Doc, Radboud University

"I use text to study the emergence of cooperative relations and social norms, as well as media representation of different social groups. While Large Language Models are invaluable for text analysis, transparent open-source model infrastructure is key to protecting scientific data without sacrificing computational power. The Macroscopic will be crucial for achieving this."

Example 4: Tracking complex transmedial narratives

Existing research in the Netherlands has shown that close reading of media content, combined with large scale experiments and analyses can yield key insights into how individual behaviours are shaped by the media and political environment¹⁹. Yet such research is often confined to single platforms and ignores the degree to which phenomena propagate across platforms, a key element of contemporary web culture. In political science, for example, modern populist movements have confounded researchers because of the unpredictable opinion trajectories inherent in high-choice media environments²⁰. Study designs that incorporate transmedial data alongside structural data are exceptionally difficult to implement, and this is true for large scale quantitative studies as well as digital ethnographies and qualitative methods. The Macroscopic will help scientists and scholars examine complex social dynamics that span multiple media platforms by harvesting detailed, multimedial, digital trace data (Task 2.3). This will be collected via web-scraping tools, the Netherlands Media Corpus, and data donation platforms linked to high quality survey data (Task 2.1 & Task 2.2). This data will then be used to fine-tune existing LLMs such as GPT-NL, which will then be usable as annotation tools and generative agents within research (Task 3.1). Using multiple LLMs as "mixtures of experts" is an active research area and typically leads to increased performance compared to single LLMs. Evaluation of their performance against specific tasks will be facilitated by a benchmarking platform (Task 3.2). In combination, these facilities will allow researchers to closely examine transmedial narratives such as how trending topics in social media and podcasts are taken up, adapted, and amplified by traditional media such as TV and radio.

Nathalie Fridzema, PhD Candidate, University of Groningen

"Pursuing a PhD in contemporary media involves navigating transmedial events in various overlapping databases, media types, search systems, and levels of accessibility. Much of my time is spent orienting myself amongst the available resources and making connections, but it is inevitable to overlook crucial links within the current heritage landscape. The Macroscopic manages this complexity, and establishes new insights."

Example 5: Designing effective and innovative surveys

Survey research is an increasingly challenging way to answer SSH research questions. High non-response rates, spiralling costs of data collection, and the proliferation of low-quality participant pools can invalidate even simple survey-based studies. The Macroscopic will bring together existing high-quality data collections with new techniques and methods to give researchers a data collection ecosystem that is flexible, informative, and efficient. ODISSEI already provides access to the high-quality LISS panel, in which researchers can field experiments at no charge on a nationally representative sample. Through the Macroscopic, the LISS panel will be fitted with a new GUI through which researchers can design and simulate the survey module they wish to deploy (Task 2.2). Researchers will be able to select their target population and then set out survey items or choose from an annotated question bank of pre-existing and tested items (Task 2.1). Using agents developed in Task 3.3 and derived from the models in Task 3.1, responses can then be simulated, allowing for advanced testing of survey items and helping researchers pre-empt design issues. These simulations will also provide cost and time estimates for the fieldwork design, allowing researchers to adjust the design to optimise efficiency. Once satisfied with the design, the survey can eventually be deployed in the LISS panel or other data collection platform. This dramatically reduces the barriers to entry for survey design in that researchers can rapidly understand technical and practical constraints of fieldwork in order to deploy the optimal survey module for their research question. The Macroscopic will therefore not only guarantee that high-quality evidence can continue to be derived from surveys, but also scale up the availability of high-quality surveys for the broader research community.

2.3 Coherence of LSRI

The Macroscopic integrates both existing and new services into a coherent platform. The four layers outlined above – Core, Data Harvesting Ecosystem, AI Collaboratory, and Gateway – relate to each other in various ways. They reflect differing stages of the research lifecycle, but they also relate to each other as technical components within an integrated stack (Figure 1).

At the heart of this platform is **the Core**: the data storage and flexible compute facilities from which all other services draw. The Core also contains the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph that provides a machine-readable representation of the key actors, concepts and logic in the scientific process, building upon international standards, using persistent identifiers to represent researchers, projects, institutes, funding agencies, research papers, research software, and research data; as well as the relationships among these entities. Ultimately it enables tools to be built on top of the Macroscopic Platform, such as workflow-aware AI assistants, automatic generation of API entry points within Python and R libraries for general reuse, or producing statistics and overviews of infrastructure usage and maintenance needs. We will take advanced examples from other fields as inspiration for the implementation²¹.

Figure 1 - The Macroscopic Stack

On top of this core sits the data harvesting ecosystem layer. The **Data Harvesting Ecosystem** integrates existing data, but also allows for the design of new data collection activities including online panels, large-scale survey data collections, microtasking, web scraping, media monitors, textual observatories, and qualitative document analysis. For example, existing administrative records can be used to determine adequate groups for sampling, or existing panel data can be used to investigate differential treatment effects in an economic experiment. The richness of the data already held by ODISSEI and CLARIAH ensures that this ecosystem is grown upon fertile ground, so that subsequent data collections can capture diverse data on social behaviours at population scale.

In the **AI Collaboratory**, thanks to ODISSEI and CLARIAH's requisite data governance and metadata documentation efforts, data merge into the state-of-the-art compute infrastructure at the Macroscopic Core, enabling innovative data analyses in Computational Social Sciences and Digital Humanities. Transforming these innovative analyses into robust workflows is a core goal of the AI Collaboratory. To ensure the highest standards of scientific rigour, the AI Collaboratory will focus on open source (FOSS) code, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable) data, robust testing methodologies, and tool benchmarking. This will enable computational reproducibility of all discoveries made with the Macroscopic, as well as reusability of the novel approaches developed within our community of Social Science and Humanities scholars.

Finally, at its outer shell, and facing novice users as they first approach the Macroscopic, will be the **Gateway**. The starting point for many researchers will be this simple GUI that allows users to use simple low-code versions of specific tools, browse selected metadata, and understand the complexity of the Macroscopic through numerous dashboards and worked examples. The Macroscopic Gateway has the specific aim of making this complex and highly innovative infrastructure as accessible as possible. It will help those with limited or no technical knowledge understand the potential of the Macroscopic, without the need to understand the array of APIs on offer or how to request specific computational resources using specialised software. The Macroscopic Gateway orchestrates all the individual components, drawing from the domain logic that is encapsulated in the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph. In addition, the Gateway provides training, ESLI support, and research software engineering support for more advanced users. Community-based learning and engagement will also be supported by a dedicated coordination team.

The scale and ambition of the Macroscopic requires the integration of all four layers and each is essential to its ultimate success. None of these layers would work in isolation and the Macroscopic would not properly function without the presence of all of them. They have been specifically designed to facilitate a broad range of new, innovative workflows and build on numerous existing, successful infrastructures in the Dutch Social Science and Humanities domain.

2.4 Applying consortium, researchers, research groups and other partners involved

Suitability of the consortium

The consortium incorporates the necessary expertise for the development of the Macroscopic. **Dr. Tom Emery** is the PI and has been Executive Director of ODISSEI for the past 8 years. He has an MBA in Research Infrastructure Management from the University of Bicocca Milan and is recipient of an ERC Starting Grant for the study of Childcare diffusion using computational methods. **Prof. Susan Aasman** is Co-PI, the Director of the Management Team of CLARIAH and the Director of the Center for Digital Humanities at the University of Groningen. She is the Chair of the Advisory Board of the Social Science and Humanities Thematic Digital Competency Center and member of the NWO Digitalisation Research Advisory Board. **Prof. Daniel Oberski** is Co-PI, the Scientific Director of ODISSEI, and responsible for ensuring that the ODISSEI infrastructure serves the needs of the scientific community. He is the lead of the Human Data Science Group at Utrecht University and specialises in the application of rigorous empirical methods in the study of human behaviour.

Prof. Jacco van Ossenburg is a Professor in Human Centred Data Science at the VU and has been a member of both the ODISSEI and CLARIAH boards for 5 years. He specialises in metadata interoperability and data quality assessment and will be responsible for the development of the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph (Task 1.1) and Technical Lead for the Core. **Lucas van der Meer** is the Chief Technical Officer for ODISSEI and project lead for SANE. He will be the Technical Lead for the Macroscopic and Technical Lead for the Gateway. **Dr. Roeland Ordelman** is the Chief Technical Officer for CLARIAH and leads the Research and Development Team at the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision. He has extensive expertise and experience in the development of infrastructure for accessing and analysing diverse media collections. **Dr. Richard Zijdeman** is a specialist in Linked Open Data for Humanities research and is national coordinator of CLARIAH. He will be Technical Lead for the Data Harvesting Ecosystem. **Dr. Peter Lugtig** is an internationally recognised specialist in survey research methods and the deployment of innovative new technologies. He will lead the development of large-scale data collections (Task 2.1). **Prof. Marcel Das** is the Director of Centerdata and has extensive expertise in the development of social science infrastructure, supporting the development of the European Social Survey, Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, and the LISS panel. He will lead the development of the Macroscopic Online Panel (Task 2.2). **Prof. Theo Araujo** is the Director of the Amsterdam School of Communication Research and Principal investigator for the D3I infrastructure. **Sophie Ham** is curator of Digital Collections at the National Library of the Netherlands (KB) and will be co-lead of the Netherlands Media Corpus (Task 2.3) alongside Prof. Araujo.

Dr. Matthieu Laneuville is the program manager for AI in the Innovation Team at SURF, lead for SURF in the development of GPT-NL, and will be technical lead for the AI Collaboratory. **Prof. Gijsbert Rutten's** research focuses on language variation and change with a focus on topics such as language contact, multilingualism, standardisation, and language ideologies. He will oversee the development of tools analysing the Netherlands Media Corpus (Task 3.1). **Menno Rasch** is Director of Digital Infrastructure at the KNAW Humanities Cluster and will be responsible for the integration of humanities collections and tools within the Macroscopic. **Prof. Jessica Piotrowski** holds the Chair for Communication in the Digital Society and is an expert in the impact of digital technologies and media on youth and children. She will lead the development of the Macroscopic Analytical Toolbox (Task 3.2), coordinating engineers at eScience and SURF. **Dr. Laura Boeschoten** is a specialist in social science methodology and the development of software for the secure and empirically robust collection of data. She will lead the development of Advanced AI tools for Data Harvesting (Task 3.3). **Dr. Kasia Karpinska** is a social scientist and the Scientific Manager of ODISSEI and is a renowned expert in the curation and management of research communities and the exploitation of large-scale research infrastructures. She will lead the coordination activities in Task 4.1. **Dr. Erik-Jan van Kesteren** is a specialist in Bayesian Methods and computational social science techniques. He is the lead for the Social Data Science (SoDa) team in ODISSEI and will coordinate the activities in Task 4.3. **Dr. Angelica Maineri** is a specialist in FAIR implementation and Data Management for highly sensitive workflows. She is technical lead for the Gateway and ensures interoperability and accessibility to the research community at large.

2.5 Strategy and embedding

The Macroscopic and the SSH Domain

ODISSEI and CLARIAH are the Dutch National Infrastructures for Social Sciences and Humanities respectively and are global leaders in enabling secure access to intensively linked data for scientific purposes.

ODISSEI is the only infrastructure in the world that allows researchers to field survey questions in a large-scale, open, probability-based panel of people that is linkable at the individual level to population registers and other administrative data sources. This linked

data may be analysed using secure High Performance Computing (HPC) facilities within the Dutch national computing facility at SURF. This unique configuration of compute and diverse linked data currently places ODISSEI at the very cutting edge of social research. ODISSEI is a consortium of 45 member organisations which include all Social Science and Economics faculties, Statistics Netherlands (CBS), public research agencies, and research institutes who are collaborating with the explicit aim of uniting the Social Sciences and creating a common, national infrastructure for research. ODISSEI was launched in 2016. All ODISSEI member organisations contribute to the operational budget of ODISSEI and ensure its financial sustainability and the continuity of services. ODISSEI is a federated research infrastructure with diverse components. The Microdata Services at Statistics Netherlands offer researchers access to detailed administrative data of the whole population, including tax returns, educational records, employment details, and population registers. For computationally intensive projects, this data can be analysed via the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) which is hosted by SURF. ODISSEI also supports a diverse array of data collections including the national elements of the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP), the European Social Survey (ESS), the European Values Study (EVS), and the EuroCohort project (GUIDE). In addition, ODISSEI provides access to the LISS panel, which is a high-quality, open probability panel, in which researchers can conduct experiments and link the data ex-post with administrative data at CBS. To support researchers' use of the infrastructure, ODISSEI has developed the ODISSEI Portal which allows researchers to search for data across all ODISSEI data providers. ODISSEI also operates the Social Data Science Team (SoDa) which is a team of Computational Social scientists who aid researchers in using the infrastructure.

Clariah

CLARIAH, the Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, is a distributed research infrastructure, i.e. the data, tools and services are distributed across various locations and institutes, connected, and made interoperable by a reference architecture. CLARIAH is one of Europe's leading distributed research infrastructures for the Humanities and empowers a wide range of scholars to adopt the latest digital technologies in their research. Specifically, CLARIAH brings together a plethora of rich cultural heritage data and state-of-the-art digital tools and analytical environments. These are made available to a vibrant community of digital humanities scholars. User-friendly access to large collections of data and innovative tools for the processing and analysis of these data is offered through a public register called 'INEO' (launched spring 2022) and applications such as the CLARIAH Media Suite. The sustainable backbone of the CLARIAH infrastructure is formed by a group of institutions (KNAW Humanities Cluster (HuC, represented by Meertens, Huygens and IISG), the National Library of the Netherlands (KB), The Institute for the Dutch Language (INT), the national centre of expertise and repository for research data (DANS), and the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV). All co-develop components of CLARIAH as part of their mission and are committed to providing services for a period of five years following the end of Macroscope. All CLARIAH developing partners are connected and accountable to the community of Humanities scholars in the Netherlands through CLARIAH-NL. Both ODISSEI and CLARIAH have existing and similar governance bodies, based on the recommendations in the OECD Global Science Forum report on the sustainability of Research Infrastructures and the InRoad project recommendations of the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures. The relevant governance bodies in both ODISSEI and CLARIAH unanimously approved the submission of the Macroscope proposal. The Macroscope will also be closely aligned with the development of the Thematic Digital Competence Centre (TDCC) for SSH coordinated by DANS, an important participating organisation of both CLARIAH and ODISSEI, and whose Advisory Board Chair is Co-PI of the Macroscope, Prof. Susan Aasman.

International aspects

Its vibrant Social Science and Humanities landscape makes the Netherlands a leader in the development of domain infrastructures that are highly invested in collaborations on the international level. European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) in the domain have active nodes in the Netherlands that contribute to the development of those organisations on the national and international levels. This includes CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure for Europe), which ensures that digital language resources and tools from all over Europe and beyond are accessible for researchers in the Social Sciences and Humanities); CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, which brings together Social Science data archives across Europe with the aim of promoting the results of Social Science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation); SHARE (the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe); ESS (the European Social Survey), and DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), which aims to equip researchers with digital methods to create and share knowledge about culture and society. The work of these ERICs will be supported and aligned with the Macroscope through CLARIAH and ODISSEI, ensuring further collaboration with those bodies on the international levels. The Macroscope partners are also closely connected to the European Research Infrastructure Heritage Science (E-RIHS), the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) and the Comparative Study of Electoral Systems (CSES). The opportunities that open up through the Macroscope will strengthen those strategic collaborations.

Through the Macroscope, the Dutch SSH community will continue to collaborate with international research groups that focus on broad interoperability and the use of international standards advocated by EOSC and SSHOC-EU. This effort was

initiated by SSHOC-NL, an ongoing collaboration between ODISSEI and CLARIAH, and will be continued in the Netherlands. Erasmus University Rotterdam, as the coordinating institution of ODISSEI, is also a participating organisation in the preparatory phase project for SoBigData Europe, which was added to the ESFRI Roadmap in 2021. SoBigData shares many of the same ambitions as ODISSEI in delivering the tools and resources needed to conduct cutting-edge Computational Social Science research. The Macroscopic project will also align with international FAIR implementation efforts including GoFAIR, FAIR-Impact and FAIRCORE4EOSC, ensuring further implementation of the FAIR principles in the Dutch SSH domain. Specifically, the Macroscopic will aim to align all layers with the developments in the SSHOC marketplace and where possible make data, tools, and services available to the international research community. Collaboration and exchange will be sought with comparable national efforts and institutes such as GESIS, Progedo, UKDS, and FORS.

Figure 2 – The relationship between the Macroscopic and existing LSRI Investments

Uniqueness of the requested LSRI in general

The Macroscopic project is developed in relation to existing investments in Large-Scale Research Infrastructure Investments in the Netherlands. Both ODISSEI and CLARIAH were developed out of the National Roadmap and designed to address the specific needs of the Social Sciences and Humanities, respectively. Both infrastructures have now reached a significant level of maturity and sustainability, a prerequisite for the creation of the Macroscopic. A further prerequisite has been the SSHOC-NL project which has brought together ODISSEI and CLARIAH, as well as the wider SSH domain, in a collaborative framework. This investment has intensified collaboration and established a strong basis of cooperation and interoperability. Through this project, shared interests and workflows have already emerged that focus on complex societal dynamics for which the Macroscopic is designed. This is precisely the depth of collaboration between the Social Sciences and Humanities that was envisioned in the National Roadmap in 2021. As SSHOC-NL delivers over the coming years, the returns on its investment will grow exponentially and the Macroscopic will exploit this investment to its fullest potential. The specificities of the services in the Macroscopic and the extent of their interoperability were not achievable even just a few years ago, but through the investments in SSHOC-NL, ODISSEI, and CLARIAH this new and groundbreaking collaboration has become feasible for the first time. The Macroscopic supports *specific* advanced workflows that require diachronic, complex, linked data with a specific view to an integrated infrastructure that supports research into complex societal dynamics. These workflows are evident in both the Social Sciences and Humanities and both fields face similar, shared challenges. Unlike SSHOC-NL, the Macroscopic is not designed to encompass all elements of the SSH Ecosystem but instead gives prominence to these advanced workflows. It is narrower in its focus but more ambitious and specific in its aims.

3. Impact

3.1 User groups, access policy, and capacity

Macroscopic services fall into two separate categories based on the degree to which there are limits on the number of access units. For services, such as data access or new analytical tools, where there are no limits on the number of access units, a wide-access, open science model will be used by which any researcher may use these services. In certain instances, access to

such services, like Microdata at Statistics Netherlands, will be restricted to those who can be authenticated as researchers, and constraints placed on their use of the data or tools provided.

For services with a limited number of access units, such as Microdata Access (Task 1.3), LISS panel time (Task 2.2), research software engineering support by the Netherlands eScience Centre (NLeSC) (Task 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3), or support from data scientists (Task 4.3), the Macroscopic will support excellence-driven access, through **cascade grants** that finance use of integrated services. Calls are overseen by the Grant Coordinators (located at EUR and RUG, Task 4.1) and administered through a singular, standardised call process. To reduce the burden on researchers and reviewers and to focus only on the quality of the proposal, the Grant Coordinators will ensure that applications are light (1-2 pages) and in adherence with the DORA principles. The evaluation of applications will involve a clear and transparent process with calls disseminated across the SSH community. Only researchers affiliated with an ODISSEI or CLARIAH Member Organisation are eligible to apply for and receive access grants. The call administration process will be managed in alignment with NWO protocols and best practices. The projects ranked highest for scientific excellence will be granted use of the facility. The calls will be designed to ensure they adequately target early career researchers, researchers from underrepresented disciplines, researchers working on interdisciplinary projects, and researchers from disadvantaged or underrepresented backgrounds. The Macroscopic Board (see Section 4.1) has ultimate deciding power over the allocation of grants. Beyond these cascade grants, users will also be able to utilise these facilities at cost if they so wish.

ODISSEI and CLARIAH are member organisations that are designed to respond to stakeholders' needs and are committed to delivering facilities that align with the community research profile and scientific interests, adopting a bottom-up approach. The Macroscopic has developed from extensive consultation and has been agreed upon by these members. The Macroscopic infrastructure will serve a very broad community, which consists of researchers in Social Sciences and Humanities faculties in the Netherlands, Royal Academy (KNAW), and National Research Funding (NWO) institutes such as **NSCR** (Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement), **IISG** (International Institute of Social History), **NIDI** (Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute), Huygens Institute (for the History and Culture of the Netherlands), Meertens Institute, and policy research institutes such as SCP (Netherlands Institute for Social Research), **CPB** (Bureau for Economic Policy Analysis), **PBL** (Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency), and **RIVM** (National Institute for Public Health and the Environment). The size of the community is considerable. Over **14,500 scholars** conduct research or teach in the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities at one of the 14 Dutch universities, and this number has been steadily increasing over the past decade. The scholarly community outside universities consists of approximately 2,000 further researchers who will be served by the Macroscopic, including researchers at various seniority levels with diverse scientific interests and methodological approaches.

Supporting Excellence in the Social Sciences and Humanities

In the period between 2019-2023, Dutch SSH researchers were awarded a total of 186 projects (ERC StG, CoG, or AdG). The granted projects focus on a variety of topics, including studies of the consequences of holding multiple jobs (dr. Wietke Conen, ERC StG 2023), the provision of community services in societies facing population decline (dr. Yuliya Hilevych, ERC StG 2023), how online platforms influence the working conditions and creativity of musicians (dr. Robert Prey, ERC StG 2022) or how feedback loops in media consumption influence citizens beliefs (dr. Damian Trilling, ERC StG 2020). Between 2019-2023, SSH scholars were awarded 320 VENI grants, 104 VIDI, and 55 VICI grants. In 2024, 25 ERC Starting grants were granted to researchers from the Dutch SSH community, the most among all participating countries, the second highest was Germany with 16. This indicates that the Netherlands is a leading centre in SSH research and the Macroscopic will enhance and strengthen that position yet further.

Many of these projects combine expertise from the Social Sciences and Humanities in tackling the complex nature of social dynamics and require the interdisciplinary perspective that the Macroscopic enables. An example is the recently funded SOCION programme that integrates scholarship from psychology, history, demography, philosophy, and sociology, using cutting-edge methods to generate novel insights on how shared values, complex social and psychological mechanisms, and (historically changing) institutional provisions affect individuals, groups, and institutions across levels and over time. Similarly in the Adapt! project, an interdisciplinary team aims at preparing societies for future crises by identifying the determinants of successful societal crisis responses from 1800 onwards, and creating an infrastructure for studying, designing, and implementing strategies that enable social systems to respond to significant disruptions such as pandemics, terrorism, and natural disasters. The complex nature of current societies sets the scene for the **GUTS** consortium. GUTS asks how young people successfully grow up in an increasingly complex society, despite the fact that not everyone has the same opportunities, and what are the main causes for differences in contributing to society? The consortium investigates this question from the perspective of societal neuroscience and combines insights and expertise from neuroscience, psychology, psychiatry, and sociology.

The SSH community is also actively involved in providing scientific insights to inform policy-making, as is the case in Meer Uren Werk! project, a Growthfund project, that aims at designing and testing policy interventions that will help mitigate the

labour market shortages, by removing (structural) barriers to labour market participation. Scaling up successful interventions and testing their potential macro-level effects is a task that is at the heart of what the Macroscopic infrastructure aims to achieve – evaluating interdependencies over time, at the population scale. Another example is the War in Court Project, funded by several Dutch ministries to make the files of over 400,000 people suspected of collaboration accessible to a broad audience. These successful projects in the SSH Community reflect significant investment into the study of complex, dynamic, and multidisciplinary research questions. The Macroscopic will elevate the infrastructure upon which these projects rely to a new level of interoperability and enhanced functionality. This will not only optimise the investments made in these projects but also open up fertile new research opportunities for the SSH community at large.

3.2 Services to scientific users and impact on the field

The Macroscopic equips researchers with the data and tools necessary to study *complex phenomena dynamically, over-time* and with close attention to the *interdependencies* inherent to social reality. The Macroscopic offers unprecedented opportunities for the SSH community in the Netherlands, enabling cutting-edge scientific discoveries that were not possible before such as those outlined in Section 2.2. Through the services described in Table 1 below, the researchers will be able to leverage the impact of their work, further developing their research agenda.

Table 1. Services for scientific user

Service	Macroscopic will offer:
Macroscopic Knowledge Graph	... access to the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph and overarching catalogue of all data, tools, researchers, projects, publications, materials, and compute environments
Secure Computing grants	...5 projects a year to use the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) and Secure Analysis Environment (SANE)
CBS microdata grants	...approximately 5 grants per year for free access to the microdata at Statistics Netherlands
Access to (enriched) survey data	...continued financial support ensuring sustainability of data collections such as European Social Survey (ESS), European Values Study (EVS), Dutch Parliamentary Election Study (DPES), Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP) and the Gender and Generations Programme (GGP)
LISS panel Grants	...approximately 8 grants per year for free of charge data collection in the LISS panel, and in addition, 2 grants per year to execute microtasking and/or data donation projects
Data harvesting Tools grants	...5 cascade grants per year for developing new data collection tools for online media and social media data
Analytical Tools grants	...access to workshops and training on implementing advanced analytical techniques in transmedial research and graph analysis
Manual Annotation Tools	...user-friendly access to corpus retrieval systems for the National Media Corpus
eScience Center & HuC engineering Support	...eScience Center & HuC research engineers' hands on support and free of charge participation in 'train the trainer' programme for engineering support (three training sessions per year, with 2 researchers per member organisation)
SoDa support	...free of charge support for 15 projects a year
SoDa Fellowship	...3 grants per year for paid fellowships (between 3-8 months) to develop computational skills for researchers in social sciences
CLARIAH fellowships	...3 grants per year for paid fellowships (between 3-8 months) to develop computational skills for researchers in humanities
Summer School	...free of charge participation in intensive two-week summer school programmes in computational social sciences or digital humanities for 50 participants
Training materials	...free of charge workshops (at least two a year, for 30 participants) and training materials for advancing computational skills

3.3 Impact on other scientific fields and societal and economic impact

Impact beyond the Social Sciences and Humanities

The MacroScope opens opportunities of new and deeper collaborations with the **Health Sciences**, specifically those focused on public health and environmental exposures. The Trusted Upload and Linkage Procedure (TULP) of the OSSC enables large health data sets and related FAIR data to be linked with the administrative data from Statistics Netherlands in the Secure Remote Access Environment with a link to a HPC environment. This creates opportunities for research in areas such as the epigenetics of disease, GxE interactions, and environmental epidemiology. This linkage protocol effectively enables the individuals in the Cohort studies of the Netherlands, represented in the National Cohort Consortium (NCC) and related efforts such as BIONIC,²² to be linked with the population scale network. This is particularly useful given that the population scale network includes a family layer represented as a pedigree data structure. The combination of genotypes and pedigree data from the NCC could feasibly allow for the imputation of the remaining genotypes within the Dutch population, including the historical population. If realised, this would allow for a wide range of socio-genetic studies to be implemented, examining gene-environment interactions and how these interact with social dynamics.²³ There is also a wide range of health data that already exists within the health domain that could be readily linked for analysis. This includes not only cohort data but also clinical data from hospitals and other health care providers, as well as “Exposome” data. The key insight of the exposome movement has been that the entirety of an individual’s environment plays a crucial, yet undetermined role in their health, and we therefore require a data-driven approach to disentangle the myriad environmental effects that impact human biology.²⁴ The social environment, however, has been mostly lacking in empirical exposome analyses, due to a lack of data. In collaboration with the national Exposome-NL gravitation consortium and the European Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure (EIRENE), the MacroScope will remedy this problem – placing individual lives in an environmental context that supplements the social context provided by the Social Sciences and Humanities.

Extensive collaborations will also be developed with the field of **Computer Science**. The facilities at ODISSEI and CLARIAH have generated large scale, highly diverse, high-dimensional and *networked* data into the Social Sciences and Humanities. Analytical approaches for such data are currently at the cutting edge of research, encompassing computer science’s graph neural networks and transformers, as well as the Social Sciences’ Siena models and network econometrics. Social Science and Humanities scholars require extensive training in these complex and challenging methods, while Computer Scientists need to become acquainted with the specificities of large-scale Social Science and Humanities data and the limitations it places on the practicalities of processing. To solve this, the MacroScope will provide support for the implementation of new computational methods in social research including but not limited to graph neural networks and LLMs. For instance, it will apply methods applied by Computer Scientists to generate graph embeddings that describe the network topography, position of individuals, and how this relates to a variety of node features. For Computer Scientists, the MacroScope represents a unique opportunity to assess whether scaling laws observed on other large graphs translate to the context of secure administrative data or unique, rich media collections that lie behind proprietary licenses.²⁵ Existing benchmarking challenges within ODISSEI have already demonstrated the significant added value of such computational approaches to the improved prediction of key social phenomena such as fertility.²⁶ The MacroScope will break new ground in using these novel techniques to understand social dynamics, building on existing investments and developments at SURF in establishing GPT-NL, helping them breach the data frontier that limits the development of similar models in other jurisdictions.

Societal and Economic Impact

To achieve maximum impact, the infrastructure works with a broad variety of societal partners and stakeholders using a theory of change approach and impact pathways embedded in the fundamental design of ODISSEI, CLARIAH and the MacroScope itself. National research institutes, such as the public research agencies, ministries, and Statistics Netherlands are already well established members and executing partners of ODISSEI, and embedded in its governance. CLARIAH has public institutions in the fields of culture, heritage, and media amongst its long standing member organisations. The MacroScope offers the unique opportunity to bring those collaborations to a much higher level to create impact beyond scientific breakthroughs. Table 2 describes the activities, principally organised in Tasks 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3, that will seek to maximise the societal and economic impact of the MacroScope.

Table 2. Societal and Economic Impact Activities

Stakeholder Engagement & Collaboration	Workshops & Focus Groups	Organise workshops and focus groups with relevant stakeholders to co-develop research questions, discuss findings, and explore practical applications of projects utilising the MacroScope.
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	Management & Supervisory Boards	ODISSEI and CLARIAH Boards include representatives from key stakeholder groups to guide the Macroscope's development and ensure that it remains aligned with their needs and interests.
	Partnerships	Collaborate with Public Research Agencies, Statistics Netherlands, and Cultural Heritage Institutes as well as ministries to facilitate the application of research findings in real-world settings.
Knowledge Exchange & Dissemination	Publications & Reports	Produce policy briefs, white papers, and podcasts that translate academic findings into actionable insights for non-academic audiences in Task 4.2.
	Conferences & Seminars	Host CLARIAH and ODISSEI conferences, workshops, and seminars targeted at both academic and non-academic audiences to showcase projects using the Macroscope.
	Online Platforms & Social Media	Curate websites, blogs, webinars, and social media channels to share research findings, engage with broader audiences, and foster public discussion.
Capacity Building & Training	Training Workshops	Develop and deliver training workshops for practitioners, policymakers, or community members to apply the knowledge generated by the Macroscope as part of Task 4.3.
	Educational Resources	Create educational materials, such as online courses, toolkits, or manuals, to help stakeholders implement research findings in their practices and make them available via the Macroscope Gateway.
	Mentoring & Internships	Offer mentoring programs, fellowships, summer schools and secondments for students, early-career researchers, or professionals to gain hands-on experience in applying research findings via Task 4.3.
Policy Influence and Advocacy	Policy Dialogues	Organise policy dialogues or roundtable discussions with policymakers to present Macroscope Projects and discuss potential policy implications as part of Task 4.2.
	Consultation Papers	Contribute to public consultations or policy development processes by submitting research-informed recommendations as part of Task 4.1.
	Expert Testimony	The Macroscope board will provide expert testimony or advice to government bodies, parliamentary committees, or international organisations on issues related to the Macroscope's work.
Community Engagement & Public Outreach	Public Lectures & Talks	Task 4.2 will host public lectures, talks, workshops, and podcasts to share research findings with the general public, raise awareness about research topics, and gauge the public's interests and concerns regarding the use of their data.
	Citizen Science	Involve the public in the research process through citizen science projects as part of Microtasking in Task 2.2, where members of the public contribute to data collection and analysis.
	Exhibitions & Media Campaigns	Task 4.2 will engage in exhibitions, media campaigns, or public art installations to engage the public in dialogue around the research and its societal implications.
Monitoring & Evaluation	Impact Assessments	The Macroscope Board will conduct regular assessments of the impact of Macroscope projects on target groups, sectors, or communities, using both qualitative and quantitative methods.
	Feedback Mechanisms	Use the inherent feedback loops within ODISSEI and CLARIAH governance structures to gather input on research relevance, application, and impact, and adjust activities as needed.
	Impact Case Studies	Task 4.2 will document and publish case studies that illustrate the real-world impact of Macroscope Projects, providing evidence of its value and effectiveness.

Sustainability & Legacy Planning	Long-Term Partnerships	The Macroscope Board will develop strategies to sustain partnerships and collaborations beyond the project's lifetime, ensuring continued impact and knowledge exchange.
	Sustainability	The Macroscope Board will monitor the environmental impact of its research and infrastructure to ensure that it works towards sustainable and green ICT.
	Alumni Networks	Task 4.3 will create networks of former trainees, collaborators, and stakeholders who can continue to apply and disseminate research outcomes in their work that will be supported and documented via the Macroscope Knowledge Graph.

The Macroscope's ability to tackle complex issues will boost the development of programmes that further societal progress. A prime example is the Dutch National Research Agenda (NWA), which aims to stimulate scientific breakthroughs and social change by addressing the pressing questions that were initially formulated by the citizens. The work that can be executed with the support of the Macroscope can feed into initiatives focusing on population changes and their impact on the welfare state (34), inequality (41), social cohesion (50), perception of art (67) or a very broad question of the underpinning of human behaviours (70), or creating resilient societies (addressed in a [NWA Route](#)) to name a few. A recent example of such a project is [HaiCu](#) which uses state-of-the-art machine learning to enrich and annotate Digital Humanities collections. This work will be closely aligned and conducive to the work of the Macroscope. Another is an NWA "Smart, Liveable Cities"-funded project to empower deliberative democracy groups with open data.²⁷ Supporting research in those areas will contribute to addressing the broader societal challenges described in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (for instance, STG8 – *Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all*). By opening new avenues for collaboration between Social Sciences and Health Sciences, the Macroscope will strengthen the impact of initiatives directed at improving public health in the Netherlands, for instance, through Health Holland. This initiative is part of the Top Sectors' mission of the Dutch government, which aims at improving the economic position of the Netherlands through innovation and solving complex problems.

4. Organisational and financial aspects

4.1 Organisation and Governance

The Macroscope's governance consists of the Macroscope Board, a Coordination Team, and Task Leads that are embedded within the pre-existing governance structures of ODISSEI and CLARIAH (Figure 3). Both ODISSEI and CLARIAH have existing, formalised governance structures and the collaboration on the Macroscope will be set out in a Consortium Agreement at the outset of the project, based on DESCA and adapted to ensure compliance with NWO guidelines and the Statistics Netherlands Law. This Consortium Agreement will remain in place for the duration of the project. The Macroscope will not create new permanent governance structures or new legal entities. It is a collaborative project between ODISSEI and CLARIAH as the national infrastructures for Social Sciences and Humanities. The host partner is Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), which acts as the host of the Project Coordination Team and secretariat to all. RUG acts as the coordinating partner for CLARIAH within the project. The ODISSEI and CLARIAH Boards, as well as the respective SSHOC-NL Board will ensure alignment with existing LSRI investments including SSHOC-NL. The Macroscope Board is appointed by the ODISSEI and CLARIAH boards and wholly accountable to them. Both ODISSEI and CLARIAH are also part of the National Board for Digital Infrastructure SSH (LBDI-SSH) which is accountable to the Social Science and Humanities Council which will provide a broader collaborative framework and long term strategic direction. To further guide the development of the project, the ODISSEI and CLARIAH Management Boards will appoint a Steering Board of six members (three members each) that will meet biannually to jointly ensure that the Macroscope is supporting ground breaking research across the SSH domain.

Macroscope Board (MB)

The Macroscope Board has eight members who represent the project partners from both the Social Sciences and Humanities, as well as the chair of the User Forum and the Ethics Forum:

- Tom Emery (EUR – PI, ODISSEI Exec. Director)
- Susan Aasman (RUG – Co-PI, CLARIAH Director)
- Daniel Oberski (UU – Co-PI, ODISSEI Sci. Director)
- Lucas van der Meer (EUR – CTO ODISSEI)
- Kasia Karpinska (EUR – ODISSEI Scientific Manager)
- Roeland Ordelman (NISV – CTO CLARIAH)
- Chair of the Ethics Forum (TBD)
- Chair of the User Forum (TBD)

The Macroscope Board meets ten times a year and:

- Holds responsibility for the implementation of the Macroscope;
- Drafts the annual work plan, annual budget, and annual report;
- Approves the design reports of products and services and allocates budget for further development;
- Approves production versions of products and services before launch and allocates budget for operation and further development;
- Can reallocate budget and tasks in accordance with funding guidelines;
- Can appoint partners who complete tasks on behalf of the Macroscope;
- Determines expenditures from the Macroscope operating budget and is responsible for procurement;
- Implements funding decisions;
- Manages risks in line with tolerances identified in the project plan and defines risk tolerance for the Task Leads, including financial setbacks, delivery delays, quality of partner participation;
- Manages the setting and reporting of Key Performance Indicators and performance evaluation of the project (see Table 3 below).

The Macroscope Board (MB) is the project’s highest governance body and is fully mandated by the project partners to operate the Macroscope. The group represents ODISSEI and CLARIAH and ensures effective management and operations. It is composed of leading scientists, senior managers, and technical leads. The Principal Investigator (PI) chairs the Macroscope Board.

When there is a budget issue or time overruns, the Macroscope Board will be responsible for adjusting and approving the original project plan. If disputes arise between partners, the Macroscope Board will be tasked with reconciling differences. To protect the individual interests and autonomy of all parties, a qualified majority in decision-making is required where the ODISSEI and CLARIAH directors are in favour. All Project Meetings only achieve quorum if a majority of members are present and include at least one representative from both CLARIAH and ODISSEI. The current work programme in this proposal has been approved by all stakeholders and, in the case of further disputes and lack of consensus on how to amend the work programme, the work programme as set out here provides the default parameters for the project and project partners. If disputes or disagreements remain unresolved, it is possible for a joint meeting of the ODISSEI Supervisory Board and the CLARIAH Board to be arranged to resolve the dispute. ODISSEI and CLARIAH have demonstrated their ability to collaborate successfully and fruitfully in numerous projects in recent years and there is a great deal of trust, collaboration, and shared interests that spans across the two infrastructures and the research communities that they serve.

In addition, the Macroscope Board meetings are attended by the Project Manager from the Project Coordination Team (CT, see next section) who will report on progress across the tasks, budget overruns or technical delays to the execution of the project, and where necessary recommend remedying actions including the potential reallocation of tasks and budgets within the terms of the grant. In the event that the Macroscope Board identifies a breach by a project partner, the host partner will give formal notice to such a party. If a breach is substantial and is not remedied within 30 days, the Macroscope Board may propose to declare a party to be a defaulting party and the consequences thereof, which may include termination of participation in the execution of this proposal. The Macroscope Board sets the overarching KPIs for the projects and monitors performance (Table 3).

Table 3. Provisional Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Owner	Measure	Target
Financial			
Budget Adherence	MB	Percentage spend in task budget	100%
Financial Sustainability of Services	MB	Percentage of tasks with board approved Costbook	100%
Financial Commitment of Members	MB	Percentage of SSH Faculty committed to ODISSEI or CLARIAH membership	100%
Project Management			
Staff Turnover	CT	Percentage of staff retained year on year	At least 80%
Tasks Overrunning Schedule	CT	Percentage of tasks missing annual milestones or deliverable	Under 10%
Change request rate	CT	Percentage of tasks requesting change each year	Under 40%
Technical			
Service Outages	STL	Number of service outages per year	Less than 10

DAB Request Response time	STL	Average time in hours until access granted	48
Scalability of SANE	STL	Number of concurrent users supported	200
Error Rate	STL	Rate of errors reported per user per month	0.05
User Engagement & Access			
Gateway Access	CT	Number of hits received monthly on the Gateway	2,000
Active Service Users	CT	Active registered of service users through SRAM	500
Institutional Reach	CT	Number of institutions using services monthly	50
Training Reach	CT	Number of participants in training activities annually	400
Research Output & Impact			
Publications	CT	Peer reviewed publications per year citing usage of the infrastructure	50
Citation Impact	CT	2-year impact factor of papers using the infrastructure	5
Research Grant References	CT	Awarded grant applications citing usage of the infrastructure annually	10
Collaboration & Partnership			
Membership Expansion	MB	New members of ODISSEI and CLARIAH over project lifespan	15
Supporting Collaborations	MB	Number of spin-off projects for partners over project lifespan	10
International Collaborations	MB	Number of international collaborations for partners citing Macroscopic over project lifespan	5
Legal, Ethical & Societal Impact			
Data Breaches	ELSI	Number of data breaches in Macroscopic system	None
Ethical Review Stoppage	ELSI	Number of projects not passing Ethical Review	No target
Public Engagement	ELSI	Number of event attendees per year	400
Public Engagement	ELSI	Social media follower numbers	20,000
Sustainability & Environmental			
Carbon Footprint of HPC usage	STL	Reporting of annual carbon footprint based on SSH HPC usage at SURF	No target

Coordination Team (CT)

The Coordination Team (CT) is responsible for supporting, facilitating, and monitoring the work conducted by the Task Leads. This includes coordination, finance, and the secretariat. Its work is included within the Macroscopic Gateway layer. To facilitate synchronisation across the SSH domain, CT employees will be exclusively hired across EUR and the RUG.

The Coordination Team is run by a Project Manager who coordinates the implementation of the Macroscopic work programme. The Project Manager is appointed by the MB in coordination with the host partner, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR). The Project Manager oversees the implementation of all tasks across the project, ensures they are adequately coordinated and ensures that the Macroscopic Board is provided with sufficient administrative, technical, and financial oversight to fulfil its obligations. The Project Manager is situated at EUR, acts as the secretariat for all project-level meetings, and maintains the Macroscopic risk register (Section 5.2), the Deliverable Reporting (Section 5.1), and KPI reporting (Section 4.1). The Project Manager is supported by two senior staff members who address specific areas of operations. They will be recruited at the outset of the project and report directly to the Project Manager. A Communications Manager coordinates the external relations of the Macroscopic. Many Macroscopic constituency organisations have existing work programmes which overlap with the aims and goals of the Macroscopic such as the use of new methodologies and support for Computational Social Sciences. The Communications Manager will be responsible for liaising with communication and

educational officers across all member organisations and organising events to raise awareness of the Macroscope. The Communications Manager will also be responsible for developing a communications strategy in the first year of the project. In addition to the Project Manager and two senior staff members, the Coordination Team will consist of coordination support staff to help conduct day-to-day operations. The coordination support staff will support all Macroscope staff and governing bodies with the execution of their work.

Figure 3 – The Macroscope governance structure

Technical exploitation & management

The project is structured around the delivery of the four layers of the Macroscope, containing three tasks each. Each layer has a Technical Lead appointed by the Macroscope Board, who is responsible for the technical alignment of specific tasks and ultimately the realisation of the Macroscope overall. These are currently Jacco van Ossenbruggen (Core), Richard Zijdeman (Data Harvesting), Matthieu Laneuville (AI Collaboratory), and Angelica Maineri (Gateway). They are responsible for technically integrating the work in the layer. To ensure proper alignment across the variety of tasks and project partners, the Technical Leads are each part of two teams: (a) of the Coordination Team and (b) part of the individual task teams within their layer.

The Technical Leads are coordinated by ODISSEI's Chief Technology Officer, Lucas van der Meer, who is **Macroscope Senior Technical Lead** (STL) and oversees all technical implementation work in conjunction with the CLARIAH Chief Technology Officer, Roeland Ordelman. There is a long-standing collaboration on technical alignment between ODISSEI and CLARIAH and the respective CTOs will work closely to ensure that the Macroscope aligns with both infrastructures. This includes the *IT development process* (what are the requirements, and how will it be designed), the *structure* (what constitutes an effective system design, and what should an optimal architecture look like), the *technology* (what technology is necessary, and which products can be implemented), and the *IT organisation* (who maintains the work, is outsourcing an option). Each task has a designated partner as Task Lead who is responsible for executing the work, within the risk tolerance as set out by the Macroscope Board.

The Task Leads report to, and are appointed by, the Macroscope Board. On a quarterly basis, the Coordination Team will meet with the Task Leads from each layer to discuss the progress of work and ensure the smooth running of the project. The

Task Leads are supported in their daily work by the Coordination Team, who are the central coordinating point for all cross-task-related issues. Many of the technical developments in the MacroScope have parallels in other large-scale infrastructure projects through forums such as SURF's 'Making the most of infrastructures' Innovation Zone. Service ownership (each partner organisation is accountable for performing the work as outlined in this proposal and for procuring its own materials), and intellectual property (the project partners remain owner of their work, but all of that work should be freely available to the Social Sciences and Humanities community at large) are addressed in the consortium agreement. No third-party intellectual property is brought into the project. Commercial activities within the MacroScope project are not permitted. The technical implementation of the Technical Leads in the project is informed by the User Forum (Task 4.1), the Ethics Forum (Task 4.2) and the Legal Guidance and Compliance (Task 4.2).

4.2 Financial aspects

4.2.1. Financial overview of the project

The project budget will be €22.900 million. €16.747 million of this will be directly requested from NWO under the LSRI call. The project will be co-financed by ODISSEI and CLARIAH Member Organisations through their regular membership fees and the in-kind support of their service providers accounting for the remaining 26.8% of the budget. ODISSEI Member Organisations commit to remain members for the duration of the project and represent the cash contribution of €2.5 million. ODISSEI and CLARIAH services and upgrades are managed and developed in such a way that they can be sustainably financed from membership fees alone beyond the duration of the project. To supplement these membership fees HuC, Statistics Netherlands, RUG, UL, KB, NISV, RU, and INT provide in-kind commitments for the maintenance of the specific tools that are developed. The development of new services brought about by this project will be done with the view that the resulting services must be sustainably maintained by the ODISSEI and CLARIAH communities. Member Organisations will be consistently consulted in the process. The annual review of tasks by the Supervisory Boards of ODISSEI and CLARIAH aims to ensure that the services being developed meet the needs of the respective member organisations and will be sustainably used. This is an existing, established, and successful model of shared infrastructure development in the Dutch SSH domain which has now been in place for a decade.

Table 4 – Total projects costs (€)

	Cap. inv.	Run. costs	Total
Requested NWO contribution	15,521,815	1,225,000	16,746,815
In kind contribution consortium		3,653,486	3,653,486
Cash contribution consortium	2,500,000		2,500,000
Total contribution consortium	2,500,000	3,653,486	6,153,486
Total project costs	18,021,815	4,878,486	22,900,301

Table 5 – Personnel costs (k€)

Description	Cont.	Cap.	Run.	Total	Yr(s)
Task 1.1 – DANS – DANS Software Dev 0.85 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	572		572	1-5
Task 1.1 – Meertens – HuC Data Engineer 0.45 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	303		303	1-5
Task 1.1 – VU – Knowledge Graph Engineer 0.88 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	589		589	1-5
Task 1.3 – CBS – Relationship Manager 0.2 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	135		135	1-5
Task 1.3 – EUR – Computational Scientist 0.85 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	219		219	1-2
Task 2.1 – UU – Survey Coordination Team 1.7 FTE, Scale 11 - 2p	NWO	1,145		1,145	1-5
Task 2.3 – Meertens – Data Repository Engineering 0.1 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	53		53	1-4
Task 2.3 – UvA – Media Data Engineers 1.5 FTE, Scale 11 - 2p	NWO	1,010		1,010	1-5
Task 3.1 – HuC Data Engineer Sustainability 0.42 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	HuC		307	307	6-10
Task 3.1 – HuC Engineer 0.9 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	606		606	1-5
Task 3.1 – RU – Transcription Engineer 0.5 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	337		337	1-5

Task 3.1 – RU – Transcription Sustainability 0.15 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	RU	110	110	6-10
Task 3.1 – UL – Research Engineer 0.9 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	602	602	1-5
Task 3.1 – UL – UL ML Sustainability 0.05 FTE, Scale 14 - 1p	UL	50	50	6-10
Task 3.1 – UL – UL Technical Expertise 0.05 FTE, Scale 15 - 1p	UL	54	54	6-10
Task 3.1 – NLeSC – ML Engineer 0.25 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	168	168	5-10
Task 3.2 – UL – Network Analytics Engineer 1 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	392	392	1 - 3
Task 3.2 – UvA – Toolbox Coordinator 1 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	673	673	1 - 5
Task 3.2 - NLeSC - eScience Engineer 0.3 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	202	202	1 - 5
Task 3.3 – UU – Software Coordination 1 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	673	673	1 - 5
Task 3.3 - NLeSC - eScience Engineer 0.3 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	202	202	1 - 5
Task 4.1 – EUR – CT Staff 1 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	673	673	1 - 5
Task 4.1 – RUG – CLARIAH CT Sustainability 0.24 FTE, Scale 11 - 3p	RUG	179	179	6 - 10
Task 4.1 – RUG – CLARIAH Director 0.11 FTE, Scale 15 - 1p	RUG	122	122	6 - 10
Task 4.1 – RUG – CLARIAH PM 1.3 FTE, Scale 11 - 2p	NWO	876	876	1 - 5
Task 4.2 – EUR – ODISSEI ELSI Officer 0.6 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	404	404	1 - 5
Task 4.2 – RUG – CLARIAH ELSI Officer 0.3 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	202	202	1 - 5
Task 4.3 – UU – SoDA 1 FTE, Scale 11 - 1p	NWO	673	673	1 - 5
Total personnel contribution NWO	NWO	10,711	0	10,711
Total personnel in-kind contribution HuC [Meertens, IISG, & Huygens]	HuC	0	307	307
Total personnel in-kind contribution RUG	RUG	0	301	301
Total personnel in-kind contribution UL	UL	0	103	103
Total personnel in-kind contribution RU	RU	0	110	110
Total Personnel costs		10,711	821	11,532

Table 6 – Material costs (k€)

Description	Cont.	Cap.	Run.	Total	Yr(s)
Task 1.1 – SURF – SURF Software Dev – IT costs	NWO	290		290	1 - 5
Task 1.2 – NISV – API Developer – PartnerHours	NWO	378		378	1 - 5
Task 1.2 – NISV – API Developer Sustainability – PartnerHours	NISV		216	216	6 - 10
Task 1.2 – SURF – SURF Engineer – IT costs	NWO	1,700		1,700	1 - 5
Task 1.3 – CBS – Hardware Improvements – IT costs	NWO	200		200	1 - 5
Task 1.3 – CBS – Metadata Translation – Consumables	NWO	100		100	2
Task 1.3 – CBS – Microdata Grants – Calls	NWO		225	225	1 - 5
Task 1.3 – CBS – RA Operation – Consumables	CBS		2,223	2,223	8 - 10
Task 2.1 – UU – Survey Costs – Outsourced	NWO	950		950	1 - 5
Task 2.2 – Centerdata – LISS Microtasking (cash) – Consumables	Centerdata	42		42	1
Task 2.2 – Centerdata – LISS Sample Management (cash) – Outsourced	Centerdata	1,875		1,875	1 - 4
Task 2.2 – Centerdata – LISS UI (cash) – IT costs	Centerdata	150		150	1 - 2
Task 2.3 – INT – INT Pipeline Engineer – PartnerHours	NWO	50		50	1 - 4
Task 2.3 – KB – Media Suite Engineers – PartnerHours	NWO	441		441	1 - 5
Task 2.3 – KB – Media Suite Engineers Sustainability – PartnerHours	KB		211	211	6 - 10

Task 2.3 – NISV – Audio-Visual Ingest Engineer – PartnerHours	NWO	50	50	1 - 4	
Task 2.3 – UvA – Software Dev Calls – Calls	NWO		150	150	1 - 5
Task 3.1 – INT – Toolbox Developer - Hum – PartnerHours	NWO	536		536	1 - 5
Task 3.1 – INT – Toolbox Maintenance – PartnerHours	INT		183	183	6 - 10
Task 3.3 – UU – Software Development – Outsourced	NWO	390		390	1 - 5
Task 4.1 – EUR – ODISSEI CT Costs (cash) – Consumables	NWO	85		85	1 - 5
Task 4.1 – RUG – CLARIAH CT Costs – Consumables	NWO	75		75	1 - 5
Task 4.3 – RUG – Fellowships DHC – Calls	NWO		300	300	1 - 5
Task 4.3 – UU – Fellowships – Calls	NWO		550	550	1 - 5
Total material contribution NWO	NWO	4,811	1,225	6,036	
Cash Contributions from ODISSEI Members (See Co-funding Letters)	EUR	2,500	0	2,500	
Total material in-kind contribution CBS	CBS	0	2,223	2,223	
Total material in-kind contribution KB	KB	0	211	211	
Total material in-kind contribution INT	INT	0	183	183	
Total material in-kind contribution NISV	NISV	0	216	216	
Total Material costs		7,311	4,057	11,368	

4.2.2. Financial feasibility and sustainability

The MacroScope will be developed between years 1-5. During this time period the twelve tasks will make significant investments in the improvement and integration of the MacroScope and its four layers. After this initial period of development, during years 6-10 ODISSEI and CLARIAH have committed to maintain core services that sustain the infrastructure via in-kind contributions for running costs, supported by written affirmations in the annex of this proposal. SURF maintains elements as part of its mandate by the Dutch higher education institutes; therefore, a formal affirmation is not needed. ODISSEI and CLARIAH member organisations are firmly committed to the continuity of their respective infrastructures and the integrated services that the MacroScope will deliver. The lifespan budget is provided in Table 7. In years 6-10, the MacroScope will be fully functioning and operational and usable by the Dutch research community at large. Since the MacroScope is not a physical infrastructure but a federated digital and human one, disentanglement, legacy and decommissioning costs are not applicable. In 2035, ODISSEI and CLARIAH will take responsibility for the maintenance of the components constituting the MacroScope and will finance their upkeep through membership revenues.

Table 7 – Lifespan costs (k€)

Description	Contributor	Yr 1-5 (k€)	Yr 6-10 (k€)	Total (k€)
		Requested	Committed	
Requested NWO contribution	NWO	16,747	0	16,747
Cash contribution	Own	2,500	0	2,500
Running Costs				
	CBS	0	2,223	2,223
	HuC	0	307	307
	UL	0	103	103
Transcription Sustainability	RU	0	110	110
API Developer Sustainability	NISV	0	216	216
Media Suite Engineers Sustainability	KB	0	211	211
Toolbox Maintenance	INT	0	183	183
CLARIAH CT Sustainability	RUG	0	301	301
Total costs		19,247	3,653	22,900

5. Technical aspects

5.1 Technical feasibility

The Macroscopic Core

Task 1.1 Data Archiving and Retrieval [Lead: DANS; Partner: VU, SURF, HuC]

The Macroscopic Core operates using a federated data structure in which data owners retain rights and responsibilities for data management. ODISSEI and CLARIAH have established data discovery portals (ODISSEI Portal, INEO), in which metadata from key datasets available to the SSH research community are documented, enriched, and harmonised to make them easily findable for reuse. In this task, the existing components will be brought to a higher level of maturity with the implementation of machine-actionable services to support easier secure onward usage of data throughout the Macroscopic Core. Components that thus far have been integrated will be redesigned as independent federated modules that communicate via APIs. This is in line with envisioned international developments where components for data archiving, metadata storage and search will be loosely coupled and interact using APIs in the future.

[1] **Data access, authentication, and processing [SURF]** – The ‘Data Access Broker’ (DAB) harmonises and automates the communication between data providers, researchers, and infrastructure providers to enable the reuse of data. This includes technical work to automatically process access information and authenticate users as well as work within the community to implement standards. Modern federated identity and access management services (e.g. SURF Research Access Management - SRAM) allow us to specify access to various compute services, but not yet to data. This sub-task will build on existing work nationally in SSHOC-NL and on the European level (i.e. FAIR-Impact, CEESDA, Elixir, Galaxy, EOSC) to match access requirements from the data provider (scientific or non-scientific) with the technical specifications of the available processing environments (Task 1.2 & 1.3) using existing models, like the ODRL ontology. This will create a unified view on data access across data providers and compute services, and provide seamless access for scientists and secure provision of data in appropriate compute environments. [Material Costs – €290k]

[2] **Metadata portal and data discovery [DANS & HuC]** – We will improve simple data discovery by adapting the search functionality within the existing infrastructure used across the SSH data ecosystem (building on the ODISSEI Portal, INEO). By decoupling the components that store the metadata from the search engines that search through them, more possibilities arise to finetune the search possibilities as we can connect different search tools with the metadata database. We will experiment and iteratively develop a more optimised search environment so that researchers actually find the data they are interested in. Collections of Cultural Heritage institutes are held and controlled locally, and largely findable in INEO. HuC will work on connecting these INEO datasets to the infrastructure developed by DANS, to allow for automated metadata ingestion and aggregation as well as onward functionality of the Data Access Broker. We aim to better facilitate within-dataset-search and increase metadata granularity on the item level. Through the portals maintained by DANS and HuC, the Macroscopic Core metadata will be made available internationally, and we aim to intensify the connection to European infrastructures including CEESDA and the EOSC marketplace. [1 FTE for 5 years]

[3] **Macroscopic FAIR Knowledge Graph and enrichment [VU & HuC]** – To ensure that data access is as seamless for users as possible, we will ensure that data access is formally integrated in scientific workflows used by researchers using open standards. We will build a set of core Knowledge Graph data and software components that provide access to all information within Macroscopic Core, and relevant knowledge graphs outside the Macroscopic Core. We will develop a set of ingestion pipelines that can be used to extract, transform and load information into our Macroscopic Knowledge Graph²⁸ as well as synchronisation protocols so we can keep duplicate instances of third-party knowledge graphs up to date. We will build on existing disciplinary infrastructures (e.g. Galaxy) and encoding standards (e.g. RO-Crate). The Macroscopic Knowledge Graph will include linked information about data, tools, publications, and workflows used in a given research project. The resulting knowledge graph will be a vital feature of the Macroscopic Core, tying together diverse elements of infrastructure in integrated and reconfigurable workflows alongside the INEO Portal developed in CLARIAH and ODISSEI Code Library. Once operational, the Knowledge Graph will be hosted and maintained by the Coordination Team at EUR [1.18 FTE for 5 years]

Task 1.2 Secure Computing [Lead: SURF, Partners: NISV]

Analysing data that is of sensitive nature, such as personal data, copyrighted data, or medical data, requires the use of secure computing facilities to ensure the safety and protection of the data in the environment in which researchers conduct computational experiments. The analysis supported by the Macroscopic Core highly depends on the availability of intensively linked, complex, sensitive data from a wide range of sources and therefore security, high levels of mutual trust, and common standards and protocols are the primary concern with regards to computing facilities. The overall aim for this task is: (1) to

unify the access to FAIR data repositories and various compute systems, (2) to integrate these various compute systems into the MacroScope.

[1] Supporting Automated Pipelines with SANE [SURF] – The envisioned automated pipelines within the MacroScope require more streamlined and automated use of secure computing environments to perform certain lightweight tasks directly “at the fingertips of the researchers” and automated curating, linking of pre-existing pipelines from a Simple GUI. These types of tasks need to be possible without context switching even if the actual computations are performed at diverse infrastructure providers. The current way of working with secure computing environments, such as SANE (manual creation of resources, staging of data from the FAIR data repository by the provider, manual logging into a portal, manually triggering the analysis) is impractical for this purpose. This subtask will deploy a catalogue of ready-to-use modules that can be launched on-the-fly from a single interface and drastically simplify the process of starting a project for an accredited researcher. Building on the SURF Research Cloud ecosystem, this will reduce the time to spin up and populate SANE environments, provide the tools to create, review and share these catalogue items, and create a scheduling mechanism to handle pipeline requests through container orchestrators like Nomad or Kubernetes. This work will support hardware-based TRE standards, as defined by the Confidential Computing Consortium and privacy preserving software tools such as Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), Multi-Party Computation (MPC), remote data execution through virtual workers and PointTensors. We also plan to experiment with using cryptographic computations directly within data pipelines. Support for reproducibility of workflows will stem from existing efforts in standardising data and software governance (e.g. RO crates). **[Material Costs – €700k]**

[2] Federated SANE [SURF & NISV] – This subtask will adapt the SANE architecture to support federated learning workflows, enabling training over datasets from multiple FAIR data repositories and from multiple providers that are not able to combine data in a single environment. In federated learning, data is distributed, and a suitable algorithm can analyse the entire dataset without centralising.³⁰ There are existing frameworks such as the ‘Personal Health Train’ that provide the necessary tools to perform federated learning workflows, but the ‘node’ at which the data will end up might not fulfil the basic safety requirements that a data provider would want. SANE uses recognised and established standards that are widely adopted in ODISSEI and CLARIAH and follows international standards such as SATRE. This means that SANE can be used as a secure environment to act as such a node, guaranteeing that data does not leave the environment, but at the same time allowing federated learning workflows to communicate to the SANE of other nodes. This work will make use of existing work such as Vantage6, PySyft, Flower, Research Drive, Yoda and SRAM and will be closely aligned with the development of the Data Access Broker in Task 1.1. Specific focus will be placed on deploying a federated SANE to enable distributed learning and queries across Cultural Heritage Institutes including the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), the National Archive (NA), the National Library of the Netherlands (KB) and the Dutch Language Institute (INT). Specifically, this will enable the fine tuning of GPT-NL on the Netherlands Media Corpus. **[0.6 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €500k]**

[3] Generalising the OSSC [SURF] – The MacroScope will provide a scale out solution for large-scale computations in the SSH domain with sensitive data. The OSSC is a highly successful bespoke solution to scale out the Remote Access Environment at Statistics Netherlands (CBS RA) on a virtual secure cluster on the Dutch National Supercomputer (Snellius) at SURF. In this subtask, this service at SURF will be generalised for other data provided beyond CBS and make Snellius available via SANE and the SURF Research Cloud. A general purpose OSSC would improve sustainability of the secure supercomputing service at SURF. Two options will be explored. First, the use of SANE as a generic steppingstone environment for a general purpose OSSC. A SANE-to-Snellius VPN can be set up to provide the same construct as the current CBS RA to OSSC setup. Second, it will be explored whether Snellius can be integrated as a backend provider in SURF Research Cloud to spin up SANE-like environments on Snellius. The security measures that are implemented in SANE and the general purpose OSSC will be harmonised and in the future could be reapplied in other types of computing facilities (e.g. high-throughput), and other (non-SURF) compute environments. This allows for environments to be interchangeable and only the scale and type of the computation to be the deciding factor for the researcher when choosing computing facilities. This will require the integration of Slurm API with the SURF Research Cloud and enable a number of functional improvements in the OSSC, including automation of project onboarding and the requesting of new software packages. This will specifically enable the training of Large Language Models such as GPT-NL on data that is considered restricted in some form. **[Material Costs – €500k]**

Task 1.3 Storage, Access, and Workflows with highly sensitive data [Lead: CBS, Partner: EUR]

One of the unique features of the MacroScope is the incorporation of intensively linked, highly sensitive data. This is individual level, administrative data held by Statistics Netherlands and accessed under the conditions of the Statistics Netherlands Law and in compliance with the five safe framework. This occurs in a highly constrained and secure CBS RA. This is similar in design to SANE but is operated exclusively by Statistics Netherlands. The sensitive nature of the data available for research purposes necessitates that the data infrastructure is operated directly by Statistics Netherlands and machine actionable and automated workflows need to be demonstrably robust and secure before entering operation and Statistics Netherlands retains full operational control and oversight at all times. All projects are evaluated by Statistics Netherlands to ensure compliance with the Statistics Netherlands Law and five safes principles. These stringent requirements make the operation of secure and automated workflows and computational infrastructure particularly difficult to achieve. Specifically

the data itself cannot be fully integrated in broader scientific workflows. This task is dedicated to ensuring that the complex and intricate workflows of the MacroScope are in full compliance with the legal, ethical, and technical requirements of Statistics Netherlands.

[1] Metadata Enrichment of Administrative Data [CBS] – The administrative data held by Statistics Netherlands is sensitive because it is extremely rich, detailed, and generated through the administrative processes of the state rather than directly for scientific purposes. These factors necessitate specific and extensive pre-processing of metadata that accurately describe what the data captures, how it relates to other data, and the very intricate and specific provenance of these data records. In addition, the administrative metadata generated by Statistics Netherlands is almost exclusively produced in Dutch whilst the vast majority of metadata from other sources is written in English. In this subtask, the metadata for data held by Statistics Netherlands will be greatly enriched with new provenance fields, the incorporation of broader methodological documentation, detailed fields on licensing and access conditions, and the addition of Statistics Netherlands Code Lists. This will ensure a high level of FAIR, enabling machine actionable metadata across the MacroScope. We will align with international code lists through Eurostat. Statistics Netherlands will also work closely with DANS in Task 1.1 to ensure that all metadata is translated into English and that the enriched metadata is included in the MacroScope Knowledge Graph. [0.1 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €150k]

[2] Automated Output Check and Model Evaluation [CBS] – One of the primary constraints on the implementation of complex, automated workflows using Statistics Netherlands data is the requirement for manual disclosure checks of all outputs from the RA. Statistics Netherlands has developed automated checks for limited data frames which will enter into service as of early 2025. However, a considerable challenge still exists in the evaluation of large-scale models trained on Statistics Netherlands data. Overcoming this bottleneck is vital for supporting a wide range of MacroScope functionalities, including the creation of new sampling algorithms (Task 2.1), the compression of large, dynamic network data (Task 3.3), and the use of Generative Adversarial Networks to create synthetic data files for training and development (Task 4.2). In this subtask a pragmatic approach will be used to develop semi-automated means of evaluating models and algorithms and the degree to which they are in line with Statistics Netherlands Law. The existing challenge with such automated procedures is that there is an inherent trade-off between disclosure risk and the scientific utility of the resulting algorithms. Statistics Netherlands will iteratively develop evaluation methods and criteria focused first on limited utility algorithms for proof-of-concept purposes, before incrementally increasing the complexity of algorithms after the execution of adversarial testing and demonstration of applicable workflows. The results will be shared widely with the international community through the IPDLN, RDA, and CESSDA with a view to setting international standards. [0.1 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €150k]

[3] Novel Macroscopic Workflows using Sensitive Microdata [EUR] – This task will support novel workflows in three ways. First, a sampling expert will develop, simulate, and evaluate a range of new sampling algorithms and particularly those utilising population scale networks. These will then pass through a disclosure check at CBS and made inwardly available for Tasks 2.1 and 2.2. Second, the Scientific Manager of ODISEI will administer an open call for grants for innovative use of the microdata held by Statistics Netherlands. This will result in the award of approximately 5 grants per year. These awarded projects will help focus the innovations in the other subtasks and will drive innovative use of the MacroScope. Third, the Scientific Manager will work closely with Computational Scientists and Statistics Netherlands to identify key hardware requirements for compute and storage that will be continuously enhanced in line with the needs of the research community. This hardware will be owned, operated and maintained by Statistics Netherlands. Specifically, this will include the addition of GPUs to the range of hardware resources available to researchers and the provision of 50TB of storage capacity for the research community to store outputs within the secure remote access environment (CBS RA). The metadata for such outputs will be catalogued in the ODISEI Portal through the Code Library and integrated within the MacroScope Knowledge Graph alongside accompanying code, standardised workflows, and related publications. [0.85 FTE for 2 years, Material Costs – €225k]

Data Harvesting Ecosystem

Task 2.1 Next Generation Data Collection [Lead: UU]

The MacroScope will implement innovations in long-running data collections. It will help researchers, policy makers and the general public to understand how the Netherlands is changing in the short and long term, whilst cementing the Netherlands' position as a global leader in social science digital technologies. The Netherlands has a central position in the European social science research landscape and through ODISEI participates in the European Social Survey (ESS), European Values Study (EVS), Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP) and the Gender and Generations Programme (GGP), as well as financing national data collections such as the Dutch Parliamentary Election Study (DPES). These data collections must be continued as they transition through a period of unprecedented turbulence and uncertainty. The pervasive nature of

digital technologies is changing the way we perceive the world, what we value and what policies we will vote for. Data will be openly available to the research community, allowing new questions to be asked, deepening our understanding of how an increasingly digital world affects society.

[1] Integrating new technologies in large-scale data collection [UU] – Recent changes in the legislative framework for the processing of personal data, including the GDPR, the Data Governance Act, the AI act, and the Data Services Act, create a framework for securely and safely collecting and linking high-resolution new data types on a plethora of social phenomena. These new streams of data have the potential to revolutionise our understanding of social processes. In collaboration with Task 1.1, Task 2.3, and Task 3.3 the Netherlands' existing infrastructure for data collections will be enhanced through technological innovations in the sphere of big data. The international survey research projects supported by ODISSEI will be connected to each other, and new technologies will be developed and implemented that serve the broader Social Science community in the Netherlands. Tools for capturing media diets and linking survey data with broader multimodal data will be implemented in long-standing surveys to complement Task 2.3 and answer pressing social science questions that increasingly centre on how people shape, interact, and are affected by technologies and the digital world. As an example, within the DPES, digital behavioural data on news consumption and social media profiles will be collected for respondents, allowing the study of filter bubbles, algorithms, and effects on political attitudes and behaviour. Similarly, in SHARE and GGP, we will link to biomedical data linked to fertility and healthy ageing for respondents. [1 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €400k]

[2] Hard-to-reach groups [UU] – Alignment with Task 1.3 will allow for the development of new sampling algorithms that help identify and target under-represented and hard-to-reach populations. These algorithms can be trained on linked administrative data in the Statistics Netherlands Remote Access Environment and then, subject to disclosure checks and alignment with Statistics Netherlands sampling protocols, exported and used in sampling processes for large-scale surveys. This could allow for new sampling approaches such as community detection and graph sampling methods to be used in the design of large-scale data collections with potential onward application in Task 2.2. This in turn will enable more efficient and effective sampling designs that target some of the most vulnerable and hard-to-reach populations. A core goal of the Social Sciences is to study subgroups within the population that are underrepresented, marginalised or difficult to reach. The Netherlands Institute for Social Research (SCP), for example, tries to evaluate whether social policies work for all. It has become increasingly difficult to reach people with low literacy skills or low levels of trust in institutions, partly because most of the research in the Social Sciences is conducted via the web. This task concentrates on implementing methods across large-scale data collections that are effective in reaching these hard-to-reach groups in an ever more digitised world, and data collection landscape. It includes testing variations of push-to-web²⁹, methods that use web- and paper-and-pencil data collection, as well as the use of face-to-face interviewers on location that are proven to be effective at reaching hard-to-reach groups. [1 FTE for 2 years, Material Costs – €400k]

[3] NL Survey Alignment [UU] – In this task, the management of the existing surveys is consolidated via two concrete steps. First, an NL Survey Team will coordinate the tendering, sampling, and coordination of all surveys, and integrating surveys in terms of content. Currently these are done by national coordinators of the respective surveys but from 2026, this will be integrated in a single team. A main reason surveys are slow is the time it takes to tender fieldwork, sample respondents from the population register (through RvIG, the National Service for Identity Data) and organise fieldwork. In many situations nowadays, the timeliness of surveys is very important, such as when an early election is called (DPES), or when attitudes towards quickly changing government policies need to be monitored (e.g., in the context of COVID-19). The Survey Team will harmonise the surveys procedurally and increase efficiency. Second, the Survey Team will focus on integrating the surveys in terms of content. The current data collections cater to different groups of end-users in the Social Sciences, Biomedical Sciences and Humanities, and each have a different focus such as social attitudes, ageing or politics. Some important research questions span multiple areas and are currently not answerable using data from one survey alone. In this task, we will integrate surveys by concurrently fielding questionnaires in subsets of the LISS panel alongside the main data collection so that researchers are able to study relations between topics asked in the different surveys. This includes comparing different operationalisations of similar constructs asked in multiple surveys, comparing the quality of the different operationalisations, and fielding more harmonised questions wordings across the different surveys.³¹ The result will be a Question Bank including indicators of question quality, provenance, and technical parameters for onward use in the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph and Task 2.2. [1 FTE for 2 years, Material Costs – €150k]

Task 2.2 Towards a Macroscopic Online Panel [Lead: Centerdata]

The LISS panel is a fundamental component of the Macroscopic and a means of acquiring copious amounts of representative, self-reported, factual and opinion-based information. ODISSEI has extended the functionality of the LISS panel to make it broadly accessible to the entire research community and enable the fielding of innovative data collection experiments such as data donation of sensor and digital trace data, voice responses and audio transcriptions via Speech-to-Text, as well as real-time, interactive mass online experiments. In the Macroscopic, the functionality of the LISS panel will be further extended in three ways. Taken together these three innovations, detailed below, will cement the position of the LISS panel as

a world leading Social Science infrastructure and dramatically increase the functionality of the Macroscope and the ability of Social Science and Humanities scholars in the Netherlands to go well beyond the state-of-the-art.

[1] **An Online Panel for Macroscopic Analysis [Centerdata]** – A new GUI for the LISS panel will be developed and deployed, as an integral part of the Macroscopic Gateway. Researchers will be able to design a LISS panel module, evaluate its costs and feasibility, simulate results and item quality, before submitting the experimental design to Centerdata for execution. The GUI will capture the study design using DDI standards and allow for the integration of tools from Task 3.1. Users will be able to set the parameters of their experiment (i.e. sample size, stratification, timing of fieldwork, longitudinal structure, etc.) via a simple online form and either create their own items or select items from existing studies, as catalogued by Task 2.1 and the CESSDA Question Bank. Once a study is designed, question quality predictors and survey simulation techniques based on LLMs will be used to simulate the results of the study and present these to users. If satisfied with the cost estimates and simulated results, users can then submit their study design to Centerdata for confirmation and book their available panel time. [Material Costs – €150k]

[2] **Network Sample Piloting & Evaluation [Centerdata]** – In conjunction with Task 1.3 and Task 2.1, Centerdata will evaluate the feasibility and potential for the use of new sampling algorithms for use in extending the sample of the LISS panel through boosters. Currently, booster samples are simply designed by sampling populations as an inverse of their propensity to respond to LISS panel Core Questionnaires over time. Whilst statistically parsimonious, this can be an exceptionally inefficient method of sample design and potentially compounds the issue of hard-to-reach groups. This subtask will simulate a variety of new sampling strategies for their statistical parsimony, scientific value, and economic sustainability before deciding on a fundamental design for future LISS sample expansion. This will include an evaluation of whether the algorithms align with the processes and procedures at Statistics Netherlands. This will culminate in an extension of the LISS panel sample itself which will increase the capacity of the LISS panel to provide accurate representation of specific sub-populations (e.g. young people, migrants, childless individuals) but also increase the general amount of panel time for the research community as a whole. This is vital as the LISS panel has been operating at 100% capacity for at least five consecutive years. A [Material Costs – €1,875k]

[3] **Microtasking Platform [Centerdata]** – The LISS panel provides researchers with a high quality and representative sample, but data collection costs are high. ODISSEI offers early career researchers access grants to mitigate these costs. Nevertheless, the requirements of many researchers do not always necessitate a representative, longitudinal panel design. Experimental designs, feasibility or pilot studies, citizen science projects, or the completion of microtasks do not require a representative sample. Currently, Dutch Researchers have access to PANL for such data collection and microtasking. In this task, Centerdata will link to and help scale this Microtasking Platform infrastructure and populate with a non-probability participant pool encompassing the general population and students to which the Dutch Research Community can field pilot studies, survey designs and experiments. Once fully operational, this Microtasking Platform will be accessible via the same GUI as the LISS panel. This participant pool will dramatically increase the flexibility of the Macroscope and will be particularly useful for Tasks 3.1 and 3.2 as media, web, and text content can be submitted to the Microtasking Platform for manual annotation and ground truthing. This platform will also draw on many of the data collection tools that are developed in Task 3.3 including participant payment and access authentication tools. [Material Costs – €42k]

Task 2.3 The Netherlands Media Corpus [Co-Lead: UvA & KB, Partners: NISV, INT, HuC]

Integrating the vast and dynamic array of media in all its forms and formats into a unified Netherlands Media Corpus is central to the Macroscope. This corpus includes a wide range of data types: some are archived, maintained, and made available by research and heritage institutions, while others are non-curated and, if at all, only partially accessible through online sources. The data spans text, audiovisual and born-digital formats, each governed by technical, ethical, and legal constraints. Managing this diversity necessitates complex workflows with advanced dynamic capture capabilities. Furthermore, this data is a fundamental bridge between research in the Social Sciences and Humanities, a common ground where complimentary approaches and perspectives come together. The Netherlands Media Corpus will be designed and implemented conjointly by ODISSEI and CLARIAH. The Macroscope will empower Social Science and Humanities researchers in the Netherlands to seamlessly access widely distributed and often restricted media datasets, study these sources in relation to one another, and integrate their own media datasets into a cohesive research framework. In this way, the Netherlands Media Corpus will evolve into a collaborative, dynamic ecosystem that is more sustainable, interoperable, and agile. It will swiftly adapt to changes and developments in the online environment, enhancing its capability to support the collection and transmedial analysis of media data.

[1] **Online Media Infrastructure [UvA, KB, NISV, INT]** – Integrating online news, including websites, social media, and digital newspapers, into the Netherlands Media Corpus is an essential and innovative component of the Macroscope. The Online Media Infrastructure builds on and expands previous PDI-SSH projects like TwiXL and CAT4SMR, which maintain tools for collecting content from forum-like platforms (e.g. Telegram, Twitter, and YouTube data). While significant contributions have

been made, researchers struggle with logistical (e.g. massive datasets), methodological (e.g. complex computational techniques), administrative (e.g. platform companies increasingly reluctant to share data), and legal (e.g. how to handle web scraping) questions. The Macroscopic initiative develops new methods, processes, and infrastructure to efficiently capture and process diverse content formats from web platforms, social media, and digital newspapers. By standardising these sources, the project significantly enhances the potential for transmedia research within the National Media Corpus. The infrastructure is designed with sustainability in mind, supporting long-term adaptability while ensuring privacy, data security, and respect for intellectual property rights.

The Online Media Infrastructure facilitates workflows specifically for online media through cascade grants for new and innovative workflows with a high potential for generalisability. The flexibility and adaptability of a cascade grant approach will allow this subtask to address (a) the increasing complexity of the digital environment (i.e. more platforms, fast changes to the availability and terms of APIs, restrictions on data collection etc.), (b) the increasing relevance of multimodal content creation and consumption in the contemporary communication environment and (c) the increasing need to collect not only content but also context (e.g. context of use, algorithmic profiling and recommendations leading to and/or around the content, etc.). Data collected via these workflows will then be indexed in the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph, facilitating reuse through automated indexing and classification. [1.2 FTE for 5 years]

[2] **Text and Audiovisual Formats [NISV, INT, KB, HuC]** – Rich datasets in text and audiovisual formats, developed and archived at national research and heritage institutions, form the foundation of the Netherlands Media Corpus. For text data, the research framework of the corpus includes processing pipelines managed by INT (Corpus Hedendaags Nederlands, historical corpora) and KB (newspapers, webpages, social media). Essential media collections for SSH researchers, such as newspapers and media from online resources, are constantly expanding and continuous processing according to standardised formats is crucial, from metadata to linguistic enrichment, as well as global statistics, text metrics and frequency lists. The processing pipelines will also be made accessible to individual researchers to process and analyse their own datasets along with the Netherlands Media Corpus. Audiovisual datasets—comprising audio, video, and images— on the other hand, pose additional challenges for researchers, especially when analysing them in conjunction with textual datasets. The nature of audiovisual data, with its diverse file formats and time-based and/or spatial elements, necessitates specialised approaches across multiple levels, from archiving to the generation of descriptive metadata through automated tools like speech recognition. Additionally, effective handling of this data requires tailored interfaces for viewing or facilitating manual annotation. To address these challenges, the CLARIAH Media Suite will support researchers with stable and scalable workflows for advanced audiovisual analysis and transmedia research. This includes ingest workflows from online resources (connected to Task 1.1), machine learning capabilities (in conjunction with Task 3.1) and computational facilities (Task 1.2), a user-friendly research environment for browsing, viewing, annotating (aligned with Task 3.3) and comparing datasets, and integrated workflows for secure computational analysis (Task 1.3), such as visualisations and Data Stories, through SANE. The data will also be integrated into the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph (via Task 1.2) in collaboration with VU. This approach ensures that researchers have the tools to effectively work with complex audiovisual data in the National Media Corpus. [0.5 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €50k]

[3] **Media & Web Diets Observatory [UvA]** – Most of the Media & Web data collections available for researchers are platform-focused, i.e. they are a collection of content that was published in a specific source under a specific set of conditions (e.g. tweets posted about climate change from 2021, transcripts of a radio program aired on a specific date). While these collections already help SSH researchers answer research questions at the meso level (e.g. what was discussed about migration within newspapers in a specific period), we still crucially miss the ability to understand how the lives of individuals are shaped by (and shape) their digital environment. The Macroscopic will create a longitudinal dataset containing the media and web consumption patterns of individuals, linking content data with its consumers, and bridging between meso-level public debate (e.g., news coverage, social media posts, online discussions) and micro-level individual behaviour and attitudes. This link is established through self reporting of media consumption and data donation. Their media and web information diets will then be made available for researchers. This subtask will make the tools from Task 3.3 compatible with the Media and Web data and facilitate the collection of multimodal content. Individuals in the LISS panel (Task 2.2) will then be asked to donate their media consumption data via data donation tools and this will then be integrated within the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph, including the existing classifications for the content within the participants' media and web diets. Via data minimisation, researchers only have access to the data required to answer their research question and all analyses are conducted in SANE environments (Task 1.1), to ensure the security of the process. [0.8 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €150k]

AI Collaboratory

Task 3.1 Analysis and Annotation [Lead: UL, Partners: INT, HuC, SURF, eScience Center, RU]

The Netherlands Media Corpus will be an extremely rich source for researchers but it is also a highly complicated collection of a variety of genres and data types in multiple formats. The Macroscopic promise entailed by the Netherlands Media Corpus, whose abundance of materials allows for fine-grained interpretations of a wealth of data representing diverse groups and individuals, requires solutions that support collaboration between researchers, focused on access to the data and tools. The tools will incorporate APIs and communicative, user-friendly access protocols and also enable less technically-oriented researchers to easily access public data. This includes access to sensitive and copyright protected data in controlled environments in cooperation with Task 1.2 and Task 2.3. The tools will facilitate state-of-the-art machine learning methods and computational resources, including resource-intensive techniques such as indexing and retrieval on large text collections and using or fine-tuning Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT-NL and Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG). While current limitations exist in handling very long contexts, emerging methods like Infini-attention aim to extend context windows efficiently, though full scalability to truly "infinite" context remains a target for future advancements as computational and memory constraints evolve. Researchers will be able to easily incorporate their own research data for enrichment and analysis using the infrastructure at SURF (Task 1.2) and explore this data either in combination with existing corpora or independently. Data will be downloadable for further processing and analysis in the user's own environment, where allowed. This also requires custom-made solutions for manual annotation, depending on the specific research questions of individual SSH-researchers.

[1] **Access to Data and Advanced Technology and Computational Resources [INT, UL, SURF, eScience Center & RU]** – The infrastructure will utilise APIs for access to the data as processed in Task 2.3, based on metadata for both text and aggregated data on texts. These APIs will cover core collections such as those of the KB and the INT corpora (e.g. CHN, historical corpora). The APIs development will focus on common queries and standardised, widely used workflows. The APIs will be specifically designed to operate in conjunction with the federated implementation of SANE developed in Task 1.2. This will enable federated learning across multiple, distributed Corpora that are currently only accessible bilaterally. In addition, an innovative RAG database infrastructure will be created by INT for the diachronic analysis of data. Secure remote analytics can also be enabled, further allowing computations to be performed on sensitive data without the need for local access. Privacy-preserving techniques, including encrypted computations and differential privacy, ensure that data remains secure throughout the analysis process, guaranteeing confidentiality while enabling collaborative research.³² In addition to tools that enable data access, there will be a range of tools incorporated that are focused on the application of advanced methods and for utilising significant computational resources. This applies to both textual and eventually oral data, thus covering various layers of GPT-NL and the Netherlands Media Corpus. Tools to be included cover topic modelling, sentiment analysis, opinion mining, trend analysis, and various forms of text labelling. Particular attention will be given to tools for efficiently training and fine-tuning Machine Learning models, including LLMs and RAG methods and supported by Research Software Engineers at the eScience Center and SURF. Such tools are essential for diachronic corpus analysis that the Macroscope is designed to address. RAG systems couple LLMs to structured databases, allowing for a seamless combination of structured, moderated, and curated data in databases with the communicative access that LLMs provide. This access point will be accessible only to authenticated researchers via SRAM. A diachronic RAG system based on temporally organised and linked metadata will enable communicative access to different linguistic strata. Additionally, fine-tuned LLMs can often accurately perform various Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks and will become core NLP tools within the Macroscope. [1.8 FTE for 5 years]

[2] **Flexible Annotation Platform [HuC & eScience Center]** – Macroscopic insight does not only depend on generic solutions, but also on detailed and specific results based on individual datasets. Therefore, a custom-made, individually adjustable annotation platform remains necessary, in addition to standardised tools and workflows, especially in the SSH domain with its wide range of approaches and research questions. A flexible platform is needed that allows for annotations of any kind (linguistic, structural, stylistic, semantic, editorial) on both smaller and larger datasets. This task will develop a common infrastructure to encode annotations, to retrieve and visualise them, to do common computations on them, to create and edit them and to share them with scholarly peers. This infrastructure will consist of multiple interoperable components on multiple levels, addressing various scientific user groups and their needs. The focus is primarily on text, but annotation of other media types is explicitly included. The infrastructure stays as close as possible to widely used international standards such as IIIF and Web Annotations. This task encompasses two core annotation clients: a generic, configurable, and standards-based collection publication interface (building on CLARIAH Plus TextAnnoViz) and a virtual research collection builder that scholars can autonomously use to select objects from online collections, organise those and annotate them (building on the CLARIAH Plus Rolodex). [1 FTE for 5 years]

[3] **User-Friendly Access for Researchers [INT]** – Tools for accessing textual data, advanced methods and computational resources are brought together in this sub-task and made available via a simple GUI that will be inwardly incorporated in the

Macroscopic Gateway (Task 4.1) so that advanced methods and infrastructure are brought within the grasp of scientists without a coding background. This will include standardised processing pipelines for personal research data in a point and click interface, as well as on-demand enrichment of material already in core collections but not yet syntactically enriched. This will provide user-friendly access to corpus retrieval systems including combined datasets via distributed learning, similar to an aggregator with corpus comparison capabilities. User friendly access will be further enhanced by analytical dashboards that include interactive visualisations. There will be documentation available for users of LLMs and other advanced tooling through a communicative interface, where users will be guided with natural language dialogues towards applicable tools and datasets that meet their demands. [0.7 FTE for 5 years]

Task 3.2 The Macroscopic Analytical Toolbox [Lead: UvA, Partners: UL, SURF, eScience Center]

Whilst Task 3.1 will put provide an infrastructure that allows for the fine-tuning of GPT-NL and other LLMs on the restricted yet highly informative data in the Macroscopic, the Macroscopic Toolbox will enhance onward utilisation of this infrastructure by integrating advanced data annotation, management, and processing tools and protocols to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR principles) of Social Science and Humanities data in the Netherlands. These enhancements will enable Social Science and Humanities researchers to leverage diverse datasets, including the Netherlands Media Corpus, survey data, administrative data, exposome data, geospatial data, and experimental data, for advanced Social Science and Humanities research and evidence-based policy making.

[1] **Annotation Advancements for Multimodal and Transmedial Data [UvA & eScience Center]** – The Macroscopic Toolbox will encompass comprehensive annotation capabilities for multimodal and transmedial data, encompassing text, audio, and visual data. Language will receive a specialised focus and tools will go far beyond the status quo to include speaker diarization, speech anonymisation & pseudonymisation, sentiment analysis, speech intelligibility measures, and pronunciation scorings. These tools will be co-developed between the Amsterdam School for Communication Research and the eScience Center. Importantly, this Toolbox will enhance the capabilities of existing infrastructures by enabling comprehensive annotation and analysis of multimodal content—from traditional media such as television and film, to contemporary web content. This expansion includes robust annotation capabilities and access to AI-driven tools for automatic enrichment and analysis. Specifically, this infrastructure will provide means to search, browse, and annotate audiovisual data sets, and provide access to tools and environments for automatic enrichment and analysis of textual, visual, and audiovisual data as well as the use of AI applications. The environment will allow researchers to work with their own data and annotate them using GPT-NL, fine tuned using the data of the National Media Corpus. APIs, in particular, will allow seamless access using SRAM to the data via the ‘Blind’ configuration of SANE and allow secure analysis of collections at the KB, the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision, and the Dutch Language Institute. [1 FTE for 5 years]

[2] **Large-Scale Graph Analytics [UL]** – The Macroscopic Toolbox will provide easy access, exploration and analysis tools for network and graph data. Existing tools are tailored to relational microdata from Statistics Netherlands, in particular the unique population-scale network data but can also be applied to the firm network data that Statistics Netherlands and ODISSEI are developing, as well as a plethora of relevant relational data, combining the rich structured microdata at Statistics Netherlands with the Annotation advancements available in subtask 3.2.1. Longitudinal population scale social network data is markedly different in its network properties than most large-scale graphs that scientists have studied before, requiring the creation of novel metrics that are substantively meaningful. It requires proper baseline tests of often used network measures and algorithms in the context of longitudinal, large-scale, population networks. Algorithms for identifying and summarising network topography and graph features will be evaluated, adapted, and published via the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph. Such tools are needed to enable scientists to find patterns in network dynamics over time. The nontrivial community structure of population-scale network can allow us to understand how community structure develops dynamically and, subsequently, how we can identify early warning signals for systemic change in the population, for example based on reconfiguring subgroups such as minorities, tying into important topics such as echo chambers and polarisation. These developments will be done in close collaboration with Task 1.3 on data disclosure techniques. Causal identification and agent-based network models will also be evaluated, adapted, and published. [1 FTE for 3 years]

[3] **Transparency and Quality Control for Advanced Tools [UvA]** – The Macroscopic Toolbox will support groundbreaking research through collaboration using state-of-the-art analytical tools. To achieve this there will be a significant focus on ensuring that the tools are well documented, and thoroughly evaluated by a collaborative community. The toolbox will include a platform to evaluate the LLM and RAG models developed in Task 3.1 against specific tasks, utilising the existing ODISSEI benchmarking infrastructure and its modular components as developed in Task 3.3. By reducing technical barriers, increasing researcher autonomy, and expanding to today’s contemporary media environment, the opportunities to support research advancements for SSH scholars in the Netherlands are notable. We will develop comprehensive training programs and detailed documentation to support researchers’ use of the language toolbox. We will implement mechanisms for continuous feedback in this process to best meet the needs of researchers. [0.3 FTE for 5 years]

Task 3.3 Advanced AI tools in data harvesting [Lead: UU, Partners: eScience Center]

To evaluate social dynamics at population scale, specialised and advanced AI tools are often required for harvesting data. For example, to run a large-scale social networking experiment,¹² to allow participants to donate digital trace data¹⁰ or observing scientists participating in a shared challenge.²⁶ ODISSEI and CLARIAH have developed several software-as-a-service solutions using a sustainable integrated approach in collaboration with commercial software developers. These software services are developed by commercial partners under the direction of researchers and integrated into an open-source platform under a AGPL-3.0 licence. As this platform has developed, an increasing number of tools within these software offerings have been reused and repurposed, generating new innovative configurations and a high level of interoperability. This approach provides resource efficient maintenance and enhances efficiency in software development for data harvesting. As part of the Macroscopic, this platform for data harvesting tools will be connected to data collection (Task 2.2) and compute services (Task 1.2), as well commercial third parties such as Kantar and Qualtrics. Crucially, this modularised system of software development will integrate the new functionalities offered by the LLMs and RAG infrastructure outlined in Task 3.1.

[1] Development [UU] – The responsibility of identifying software needs and a general work program will lie with a supervising software coordinator at UU who will liaise with the Coordination Team at EUR. Together they will develop the technical requirements and specifications for required tools and commission commercial providers to develop and deliver these. This includes the sustainable redesign of tools that were previously developed by researchers that proved to be valuable, such that they can be integrated into the Macroscopic's open-source platform. Additional third-party software services will be integrated when required and alignment with compute services (Task 1.2) and data collection platforms (Task 2.2) will be integrated where necessary, including the software necessary for the collection of Media and Web diets (Task 2.3). The availability of GPT-NL, fine-tuned on the Netherlands Media Corpus, will allow for advanced annotation to take place within these secure data donation tools. This will greatly enhance the functionality of data donation tools currently in production and enrich our understanding of media diets. Particular emphasis will be placed on tools that have generalisable use and wide applications. All tools will be developed under the same common licences and be available via GitHub to support self-hosting, adaptation, and onward innovation.

[0.3 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €400k]

[2] Deployment [UU] – Before deployment, tools will be rigorously tested and undergo quality assurance criteria, as well as UX testing. In addition, contracts and user agreements allowing for both usage through the Macroscopic platform but also for self-hosting will be put in place. This is non-trivial in many instances as the tools regularly process personal data and handle financial payments. The legal basis for the operation of these tools must be carefully developed and simplified. Finally, before deployment all tools will be extensively documented and made interoperable with other elements of the Macroscopic, including documentation of the tool using an open standard ontology and the creation of persistent identifiers for each tool. The tools will then be documented in the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph (Task 1.1) and catalogued in the ODISSEI portal, INEO, and the SSHOC marketplace. In addition to metadata, the documentation will include step-by-step interactive walkthroughs of the tools including versions for access through the platform and for self-hosting. All associated documentation will be indexed via the ODISSEI and CLARIAH communities on Zenodo and the resulting DOI's will be integrated into the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph for easy discovery. This sub-task is also responsible for security evaluations and updates. [0.6 FTE for 5 years]

[3] Support [UU & eScience Center] – Once tools are deployed, a research software engineer will aid in the maintenance of all tools hosted on the platform. Scientists will be able to use the tools hosted on the platform for no costs. However, to support initial usage and innovative workflows, grants will be issued that provide users with free engineering time to create new workflows and applications. These grants will be specifically targeted at projects that make use of integrated services within the Macroscopic. For example, researchers wishing to conduct a data donation study may wish to apply for use of specific tools and have them deployed via the LISS panel (Task 2.2), one of the survey data collections (Task 2.1) or via the Microtasking Platform (Task 2.2). In addition, short courses, documentation, and course materials will be developed in coordination with Task 4.2. [0.4 FTE for 5 years]

Macroscopic Gateway

Task 4.1 Coordination [Lead: EUR, Partners: RUG]

The Coordination Task is led by EUR as the Host of the ODISSEI Coordination Team and Project Lead for the Macroscopic. They will be extensively supported in this work by the new CLARIAH Coordination Hub at RUG. The team at RUG will be specifically responsible for ensuring that the Macroscopic serves the needs of the Humanities community, and that the Humanities community is conversely engaged and actively using the Macroscopic and its myriad of functionalities.

[1] **Gateway GUI Development [EUR]** – The Coordination Team will be responsible for the evaluation of user experiences and ensuring that the ambition of a fully accessible infrastructure is realised. In this subtask the specifications for the Gateway will be established and the coordination with Task Leads responsible for delivering services through this. Central to the smooth functioning of the Gateway will be an effective, comprehensive, and clear orchestration component, which draws its domain logic from the Macroscopic Knowledge Graphs and facilitates for seamless interoperability across services and the configuration of new and innovative workflows. This work will be led by the Gateway Technical Lead and the Scientific liaisons of ODISSEI and CLARIAH. The Gateway will be developed in conjunction with the User Forum and extensively tested and iteratively developed through an agile development process. Whilst the backend architecture of the Macroscopic will be the responsibility of the various Task Leads and product owners, the Coordination Team will be responsible for the commissioning and delivery of the overarching GUI through which researchers interact with various components of the Macroscopic. This GUI will not provide access to all components of the Macroscopic but will instead showcase demonstration workflows, allow researchers to search for data, and deploy simple, standardised, workflows. [0.8 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €135k]

[2] **User Forum & Liaisons [EUR & RUG]** – To ensure validity and usability of the developed applications, a User Forum will be established. The User Forum consists of 25 junior researchers representing the ODISSEI and CLARIAH member organisations and will be asked four-times per year to test and provide feedback on new drafts of applications that are in development. Because the participants are junior researchers, likely without a tenured position, they will be financially compensated for their time. The Macroscopic Board is advised by the User Forum before approving stages of product and service development. This subtask will also oversee the administration of all open calls within the project and issues of access. This will include the administration of calls, eliciting peer-reviews of applications, and ensuring that all grants are used effectively and in accordance with Macroscopic user policies. Finally, they will administer the community platform accessible via the Macroscopic Gateway, which will provide users with easy access to the different support and training options available [0.5 FTE for 5 years]

[3] **Project Management, Secretariat & Communications [EUR & RUG]** – Project management and communications are conducted within this task, led by the Coordination Team at EUR. The Project Manager at EUR is responsible for the implementation of the Macroscopic and reporting, both to the Macroscopic Board and NWO. The Coordination Team is also responsible for coordinating the sustainability strategy of the domain and ensuring that the necessary financial, governance, and legal instruments are in place to sustain the project's services by the end of the project. They will work closely with the CLARIAH Project Manager at RUG and will together ensure that the project is executed effectively and that all stakeholders are adequately informed and resourced. The Communications Manager organises (1) joint engagement events aimed at SSH scholars about shared themes, methods, and techniques, and (2) monthly Task Insights meetings stimulating knowledge exchange and collaboration between tasks. The Communications Manager will also (3) facilitate community building and interaction, and (4) disseminate information and project outputs via a newsletter, social media channels, a project website, and a shared events calendar. A Communications Manager in the CLARIAH Coordination Team at RUG will ensure that communications outputs are also tailored for the Humanities community and their specific requirements and community practices. [1 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €25k]

Task 4.2 Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications [Lead: RUG, Partners: EUR, eScience Center]

Many of the elements of the Macroscopic are novel and new services associated with sensitive or restricted data. This inevitably raises a plethora of ethical and legal issues that need to be managed through the project. Research organisations remain the key responsible party for ethical oversight in the execution of research that uses the Macroscopic, and the data providers remain legally responsible for data access and ensuring compliance with national and international legislation. Nevertheless, the Macroscopic will include Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) officers within the ODISSEI and CLARIAH Coordination Teams that can support, advise, and consult data providers and Ethical Review Boards across the Macroscopic Community. These ELSI officers will be available for consultations on specific projects and support researchers with ELSI concerns in executing their projects. They will also facilitate broader discussions and consultations with stakeholders and the general public on ethical and legal issues in the types of research conducted using the Macroscopic. This will be an integral part of the Macroscopic's impact pathways (see Section 3.3) as there is a distinct need for leadership, coordination, and dialogue in this area as the amount of research utilising new methods, data, and tools increases.

[1] **Ethics Forum [RUG, EUR, eScience Center]** – In the Dutch SSH community, ethical oversight is the responsibility of the organisation that employs the researcher engaged in the research and not the infrastructure that the research is utilising. Nevertheless, Ethics Boards at university faculties require support in evaluating the ethical implications of novel workflows such as those supported by the Macroscopic. The Macroscopic will therefore create an Ethics Forum for the chairs of all Ethical Committees at member organisations for ODISSEI and CLARIAH. This forum will meet once a year in an intensive two-day meeting that will highlight the functionalities of the Macroscopic, example projects that utilise these facilities and to openly discuss the ethical challenges that such workflows raise. This workshop will include external speakers with expertise in particular areas such as web-scraping, transparent annotation, replicability, bias amplification, and intellectual property.

The Chair of the Forum will be elected from amongst its members and will be independent of the Macroscopic Governance with EUR and RUG providing secretarial capacity. The eScience Center will also support the work of the Ethics Forum through its Responsible AI program, presenting on issues of central importance in the use of new AI methods in Social Science and Humanities research. [0.3 FTE for 5 years]

[2] **Legal Guidance & Compliance [EUR & RUG]** – As with ethics, legal compliance is the responsibility of the data and service providers within the Macroscopic and not the consortium as a whole. The Macroscopic is not a legal entity, it does not hold data and it does not provide services directly. However, the consortium does operate as a coordinating body and this is equally true in issues such as legal guidance and compliance. Many elements of the infrastructure involve the handling of restricted data and the adherence to security provisions within service providers. The ELSI officers at EUR and RUG will work closely with the technical working group and the data providers from across the consortium to ensure that common standards are agreed upon and propagated throughout the community. The consortium has considerable success in this area and has an established and trusted reputation. For example, through the development of SANE, ODISSEI and CLARIAH jointly documented the security standards employed by Statistics Netherlands, generalised these to international standards, adapted them to comparable workflows and through this created a coherent and interoperable system of Trusted Research Environments. The ELSI officers will therefore document, map and align the legal compliance requirements and provisions across the project and provide these to the Technical Working Group. They will also be responsible for monitoring further legal developments such as the impact of the **Data Governance Act**. [0.3 FTE for 5 years]

[3] **Public Engagement [EUR & RUG]** – The Macroscopic is designed to address key societal challenges and fundamentally to improve society's understanding of itself. In doing so, new technologies and diverse data streams are used. It is vital that the implications of these methods are discussed widely and accessible both in terms of the opportunities that the Macroscopic presents but also in its limitations and what it cannot or should not do. To support this public engagement, the Macroscopic will focus on four key activities. Firstly, a sub-committee of public representatives will be appointed for the Ethics Forum. This sub-committee will be recruited through an open public call and consist of five members of the public, selected by the Chair of the Ethics Forum. They will attend the annual Ethics Forum and be available for consultation on public perception of specific projects utilising the Macroscopic. Secondly, open public engagement events will be held annually to raise the public profile of projects using the Macroscopic and we aim to integrate these in existing public engagement series such as 'Science Night' and the Public Engagement events of the KNAW, and projects such as AlgoSoc. Thirdly, layperson summaries and press releases will be issued via the ODISSEI and CLARIAH websites on a regular basis that provide accessible demonstrations of the work conducted in the Macroscopic. [0.3 FTE for 5 years]

Task 4.3 Analytics Training [Lead: UU, Partners: RUG, eScience Center]

Enhancing the impact of the Macroscopic as a community and resource for Social Scientists and Humanities scholars in the Netherlands through education, training, and collaborative projects. In this task, we develop three interconnected work packages: sustainable support, an education programme, and federated expertise. This task will be embedded in the ODISSEI Social Data science team (SoDa) at Utrecht University and the CLARIAH Coordination Hub at RUG, with strong collaborations with Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 and other tasks beyond.

[1] **Data Analytics Support [UU]** – Accessible consultation and larger collaboration projects will be provided for the research community, with a focus on scaling up community-building and impact on research. On the consultation side, this means maintaining a high level of availability for small and larger methodological and data science questions. On the collaboration side, this means selecting high-potential projects which benefit from additional data science expertise which could not be executed otherwise. This work allows the team to act as the interface between the consortium and its research community, identifying opportunities for community learning. Examples of potential projects include synthetic data and privacy, causal inference with observational data, and the use of Large Language Models for data collection purposes. SoDa's capabilities turn these opportunities into workshops, research projects, or software, paving the way for higher-quality Social Science research. Collaborating with Social Scientists and Humanities scholars to create reusable didactic materials, such as a tutorial paper series for common use-cases of the infrastructure, such as linking LISS data with Statistics Netherlands data, porting research code to the OSSC, performing causal inference with register data, or the practicalities around analysing population-scale networks. These tutorial papers will become core resources for the Macroscopic Community and indexed within the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph (Task 1.2). [0.7 FTE for 5 years]

[2] **Education Programme [UU & RUG]** – The development of an education programme will act as a force multiplier on the impact of developments in the research infrastructure by bringing these directly to relevant users of those developments. First, an intensive two-week summer school will be run for 25 students every year, with a focus on giving early-career scientists the knowledge and skills to do research with valuable Macroscopic resources including emphasis on the incorporation of multimodal data and bridge between the Digital Humanities and Computational Social Sciences. Second, educational modules and walkthroughs from across the Macroscopic will be combined and curated to create an "essential technical skills" curriculum, aimed at incrementally elevating researchers from beginner to advanced users. This curriculum

will involve both self-guided learning and in-person sessions and can serve as a track for Graduate Level education. It will also be used by the fellows (see subtask 3) and will be open to faculty. Finally, a wide range of Social Science and Digital Humanities methods educators will be brought together in a series of workshops to compare, contrast, and collaborate on the development of interdisciplinary open educational modules. An example could be a “methods in Social Science” introduction module, which explains how different fields tackle certain problems; or a “Social Science datasets” module which provides examples of the different types and requirements of data in different areas of social science. This will allow students and educators alike to gain an interdisciplinary perspective, fostering future collaborations across fields. [0.2 FTE for 5 years]

[3] **Federated Expertise [UU, RUG, & eScience Center]** – A network of data science expertise will be established that spans existing ODISSEI and CLARIAH Member Organisations and supports research within existing Social Science faculty and centres for Digital Humanities. A fellowship programme will be established targeting early-career faculty, improving upon and integrating existing successful programmes. In the fellowships, we will not only train scientists to develop the skills and knowledge required in modern social research with large or complex datasets, but also train them to propagate these skills to others within their home institutions. After the fellowship, they will become part of a federated community of practice, providing support and expertise in their local institutions. By aligning domain expertise with expertise on data science and good research software practices, we will provide accessible and long-lasting impact across SSH in the Netherlands. This work involves grants, requiring close coordination with various parts of the MacroScope such as the coordination task (Task 4.1) and the MacroScope Board. A ‘train-the-trainer’ program will be established by eScience Center, to amplify the spread of knowledge of Computational Social Sciences and Digital Humanities making use of the MacroScope and specifically the tools developed in the AI Collaboratory. The eScience Center has recently started such train-the-trainer initiatives in other disciplinary fields and has good experiences with them. The participants for such a training can be selected strategically throughout the ODISSEI and CLARIAH networks (for example, one or two participants per university/institute) and can be trained on both how to effectively teach researchers and support staff from Social Sciences and Humanities and how to develop new training materials. [0.1 FTE for 5 years, Material Costs – €300k]

Deliverables

Across the tasks, various components that make up the MacroScope Stack will be developed. Some of these are already in production and will be upgraded or extended. Others will be entirely developed for the macroscope. Together they constitute the deliverables of the MacroScope, iteratively developed and integrated.

Table 8. Components Current Status and Deliverables

Deliverable	Lead	Current Status	Upgrade
Data Access Broker (DAB)	SURF	Prototype	Implement ODRL and expand across MacroScope Data Providers
SRAM	SURF	Production	Apply SRAM for AAI to secure API connections
ODISSEI Portal	DANS	Production	Enhanced functionality through modularised Dataverse
INEO	HuC	Production	Conversion of CLARIAH data catalogues into DANS catalogue
Code Library	EUR	Production	Enriched annotations and expansion of collection
MacroScope Knowledge Graph	VU	None	Fully implemented, published and actionable
SANE	SURF	Beta Phase	Implementation of automated workflows
Federated learning and analytics	SURF	None	Deployment of federated architecture in SANE
SANE HPC integration	SURF	None	Use of Snellius enabled from within SANE framework
General OSSC	SURF	None	OSSC protocols deployable for all MacroScope data providers
CBS Metadata Catalogue	CBS	Production	Enriched with detailed provenance and translated to English
CBS Disclosure Check Tool	CBS	Prototype	In production for assessment of model disclosure risks
CBS RA	CBS	Production	Access to research community and innovative workflows
Advanced Sampling Algorithms	EUR	None	Catalogue published through the ODISSEI code library
Large-Scale Data Collections	UU	Production	Extended and enriched with new Data Donation technologies
Question Bank	UU	None	Created and published as open-source data
LISS panel GUI	Centerdata	None	In production supporting LISS module design and deployment
Microtasking Platform	Centerdata	None	Piloting of platform, development is demand dependent

Online Media Infrastructure	UvA, KB, NISV	None	Integrated catalogue of existing tools that are aligned with NMC
National Media Corpus	NISV & KB	None	Metadata schema published allowing for federated analysis
Media Suite Transmedia Analysis	NISV	Prototype	Advanced analysis and annotation of media comparison
Diets Observatory Mapping	UvA	None	Mapping of individual habits and aggregate level descriptives of media sources
Diachronic RAG System	SURF	None	Fully operational supporting diachronic analysis of GPT-NL LLM that is fine tuned on NMC
Corpus Retrieval Tools	INT	None	Fully operational and accessible using SRAM within SANE framework
TextAnnoViz	HuC	Production	Updated and aligned with SANE framework
CLARIAH Rolodex	HuC	Production	Updated and aligned with SANE framework
Generative AI Secure API	SURF	None	Operational and Queryable through API with access managed by SRAM
Macroscopic Analytic Toolbox	UvA	None	Ready to use Annotation tools in common languages (R and Python) that utilise the GPT-NL secure API
Population Scale Network	UL	Production	Publication of tools for analysis from within the CBS RA
Port software	UU	Production	Upgraded with integration of GPT-NL secure API annotations
GPT-NL Benchmarking	UU	Production	Extended for evaluation of LLMs against specified annotation tasks

5.2 IT-infrastructure including data and software

The Macroscopic Stack consists of an ordered collection of the components that are delivered in each layer. Each sequential layer elevates foundational infrastructures closer to non-technical end users, with the Gateway enabling use by the majority of Social Science and Humanities scholars. Lower layers allow more technically skilled researchers to customise services for specific workflows. Higher layers rest on the facilities provided by deeper, foundational layers. The Macroscopic can be represented as **independent federated components** that communicate via API calls and are orchestrated centrally. From an IT perspective the Macroscopic is represented using four layers of the **Macroscopic stack** and resulting in the following components that constitute the Macroscopic.

In the **Macroscopic Core** integrated pipelines will be created so that researchers can navigate easily between four compute environments (CBS RA, OSSC, Snellius, SANE), storage (DANS SSH Data Station, NISV, National Archive, KB, and INT), access and reuse facilities (ODISSEI Portal, CLARIAH INEO, SURF Data Access Broker, ODISSEI Code Library). These will adhere to national and international data regulations (i.e. GDPR, AVG, and Statistics Netherlands Law). The Macroscopic maintains a strict separation between data and metadata. Whereas the data is almost always sensitive and managed by the respective data owners, the anonymized metadata is considered public and critical to accomplish the required **interconnectivity** between all components. The metadata will be ingested from each partner, enriched and represented using the **Macroscopic Knowledge Graph**. This builds upon an already existing foundation of related standards and best practices available within the CLARIAH and ODISSEI ecosystems and SSHOC-NL. It streamlines the metadata of datasets through Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), but also the related variables, code lists, analysis code, tools, analysis environments, individuals and organisations, concepts, research activities, models, publications, and projects. Given the sensitive nature of the data, security is a hallmark of the Macroscopic Core. Much of the data is **strictly protected** through the project's data partners that have the appropriate infrastructure in place to securely process the data, such as a CoreTrustSeal, ISO 27001 certification and independent penetration tests. The Macroscopic is not a legal entity and does not process sensitive research data; this happens bilaterally between each data provider and the user under the general framework of the Macroscopic. The compute environments follow the **Five Safes** framework. Throughout the Stack, SRAM will be used to authenticate and authorise access to data and the services. At the beginning of the project, EUR (ELSI officers in Task 4.2) will carry out a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).

Figure 4 – The components constituting the Macroscopic Stack

The **FAIR data principles** are considered a fundamental driving force behind the **data harvesting ecosystem**, emphasising machine-actionability that goes beyond basic FAIR compliance. The capacity to offer FAIR data and tools will establish a shared infrastructure, enabling the innovative, cross-domain research that is envisioned. This commitment is evident in the strong ties to European and global initiatives like the Go-FAIR Foundation, FAIR-IMPACT, RDA and EOSC. The Macroscopic requires that all partners ensure data adheres to FAIR principles and is made available "as open as possible, as secure as necessary". Any data generated must be accessible to researchers through a trustworthy digital repository within a maximum of six months after the completion of a research project using appropriate machine readable licences. Access conditions must be made as clear and actionable as possible. The privacy of respondents must be safeguarded through appropriate de-identification measures and the use of secure environments. All metadata follows existing standards and is open, machine-readable, and searchable. Both existing and new data within the Macroscopic ecosystem will be documented according to the relevant **community standards**, which will be declared in FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) as established in SSHOC-NL. Survey data will follow the standards already in place for the respective surveys, either DDI Lifecycle or DDI Codebook, depending on the survey's design. Statistics Netherlands microdata is documented following derivatives of the SDMX metadata standard used by statistical agencies. The Netherlands Media Corpus incorporates standards including Dublin Core, METS, and MPEG-7 and will publish an advanced FIP within the first year of the project. The user agreement will mandate that all projects utilising the Macroscopic must complete a **data management plan** detailing the project's documentation and archiving strategy to ensure compliance with FAIR principles. The metadata will include information on the data collection methodology, analytical and procedural details, definitions of variables, units of measurement, scientific concepts, provenance, version history, accessibility, licensing, and multilingual support. The user agreement will also stipulate that analytical code from Macroscopic activities must be made publicly available and findable.

Central to the **AI Collaboratory** is the utilisation of open Large Language Models for scientific purposes and creation of a RAG infrastructure. Utilising the core infrastructure at SURF, these models will be fine-tuned on restricted data of the Macroscopic including the Netherlands Media Corpus, the metadata of Statistics Netherlands, and compressed and anonymised representations of the Population Scale Network. When integrated with mechanisms like Infini-attention or built-in memory architectures, these systems can handle extended or "infinite" context more effectively.³³ This enhances the model's ability to retain long-term knowledge from both structured and unstructured sources, ensuring a dynamic interaction where LLMs can access and leverage vast data stores over time while continuously learning from new inputs, without overwhelming memory or computational resources. We will further investigate improved computational efficiency by enhancing retrieval algorithms to prioritise important data chunks that can minimise retrieval overhead; through adaptive fine-tuning so that we can update model weights based on task complexity, reducing full model retraining costs. Finally, applying model pruning and quantization can shrink the model size and computational load without sacrificing performance. The resulting models, hosted by SURF & INT, will only be accessible to engineers and authorised researchers using SRAM and support the onward development of a range of tools that encompass the AI Collaboratory. Tools that will be developed will be hosted through SURF Research Cloud as **SaaS applications**. The source code will be openly available in the Macroscopic Git repository with an **AGPL-3.0 licence**, easing access for the full Dutch academic community. We will adopt the open-source guidelines provided

by the eScience Center in FAIR Software. All software will be evaluated using the Open Source Security Foundation (OpenSSF) checklist. Researchers will also be able to **self-host** tools in case they want to develop additional functionalities, or if their Data Stewards conclude so in their DPIA. Where necessary and preferable, commercial software developers will be utilised under the direct supervision of the project’s Senior Technical Lead (STL).

The final layer is the **Macroscopic Gateway**, the main **Graphical User Interface** (GUI) that provides easy access to demonstrative workflows that utilise the components of the previous three layers. The Gateway enables the majority of SSH researchers to design and execute simple scientific workflows, in a single interface streamlining the communication between the individual components. At the highest level of abstraction, the Macroscopic Gateway needs to **orchestrate** a wide range of heterogeneous individual components, which use a variety of concepts, and provide a meaningful user interface. It draws from the Macroscopic Knowledge Graph, which has a fundamental understanding of the data, code, tools, environments, users, authors, concepts, publications, projects, and organisations within the project. As such, the orchestration component is a critical piece to ensure that all the components are interoperable and provides the **domain logic**³⁴ for the Macroscopic. Because of the large number and diversity of the components, they are all represented as loosely coupled independent **private cloud** components that communicate through API calls. The orchestration will run on SURF Research Cloud (SRC), using SURF HPC Cloud, Kubernetes, and OpenStack. Whereas the lower layers have a high Technology Readiness Level providing advanced functionality to skilled researchers with advanced research questions, the Gateway adds additional abstraction to create a high **Stakeholder Readiness Level** for the key functionalities of the components. In initial phases the workflows will be few and simple in nature, with increasing complexity and flexibility as the Macroscopic matures. Extensive **training and support** will be available in using the Macroscopic Gateway. The API calls also provide an **open infrastructure** and enable developers to easily connect with and extend its services.

Software management & IT costs

To manage the development of the Macroscopic many components, an **agile software engineering** approach will be applied by all project partners. The agile approach requires that end users provide feedback from the design phase of the project and on intermediate versions of software components. Rather than developing in a ‘waterfall’ fashion, the project requirements and deliverables will be extended throughout the project in so-called ‘sprints’ of three months. Each sprint for every task starts with a planning phase, in which the precise focus of the sprint is determined. Next, designs of the deliverables are made using simple wireframes, which are consequently developed, tested and deployed. Finally, the sprint is reviewed, and results incorporated into the next sprint. The **User Forum** (see Section 4.1) will assess each intermediate deliverable. The IT costs were allocated to enhance infrastructure, development, and licensing across various tasks. The “Data Archiving and Retrieval” task (Task 1.1) receives €290k for software development at SURF. The “Secure Computing” task (Task 1.2) is allocated €1,230k for engineering at SURF. €200k is set aside for CBS for hardware improvements in Task 1.3. Task 2.2 is allocated €150k for LISS UI development at Centerdata. In total, the IT costs amount to €2,340k. The Macroscopic is a federated infrastructure that **integrates** ODISSEI’s and CLARIAH’s most critical individual infrastructures from various E-infra providers and makes many accessible from a singular interface, facilitating users to conduct groundbreaking research. Infrastructures that are integrated into the Macroscopic include SURF’s OSSC and SANE, SURF HPC Cloud and Research Cloud, and DANS SSH Data Station. Users of the Macroscopic core can rely on budgets from NWO for using the underlying infrastructure (the small and large NWO compute call).

5.3 Risk analysis and mitigation strategy

A simple risk management system will be established, reviewed quarterly, and regularly updated by the Macroscopic Board. Each risk identified is assigned a specific risk owner, who is responsible for tracking the risk’s status, assessing its likelihood, and evaluating the potential impact if it occurs. The risk owner will update the system as needed, reporting any concerns to the Project Manager and with escalation the Macroscopic Board where necessary.

Table 9. Risk Register

Risk	Owner	Likelihood	Effect	Mitigation
Financial				
Inflationary pressure	MB	Low	Moderate	MB will adapt Task plans annually to reflect financial constraints
Government Cuts	MB	High	Moderate	Government cuts may impair the capacity of various stakeholders
Financial Sustainability of services	MB	Low	Low	Services will be constantly evaluated against demand via User Forum and stakeholder consultation
Organisational				

Dysfunctional Governance	MB	Low	High	Annual plan and annual evaluation by MB and SB
Dysfunctional Coordination Team	MB	Low	High	Quarterly evaluation by MB
Insufficient resources for tasks	CT	Low	Moderate	Quarterly updates on budgets and progress by task leads
Dependencies between tasks	STL	Med	Moderate	Reviewed and monitored quarterly by STL and MB
Technical				
Delay in delivery of deliverables	STL	High	Low	Each task to develop contingency plans at project outset; using Agile
Difficulty integrating all tools into the Gateway	STL	High	Moderate	Using Agile methodology, loosely coupled modules
Fundamental shifts in technical capabilities	STL	Med	High	Monitoring of technical capabilities and recommendations of adapted work program to MB
Legal and Ethical				
Scientific malpractice using MacroScope	MB	Low	High	Code of Ethics embedded in the Terms of Participation signed by all users
Inadvertent personal data disclosure	MB	Low	High	Transparent and robust disclosure checks by Data Controllers
Security breach	MB	Low	High	Pen testing, continuous monitoring of security (logging) and training of researchers in the context of (privacy) security must reduce those risks
Changing Legal Framework	CT	Low	Moderate	Legal developments to be monitored by ELSI team in Task 4.2

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Applicant Publication Samples

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Number of pages - The number of pages of Sections 1 to 6 of this grant application is: 40 pages (max. 40 pages)

7. Data management

This is a standard section that is part of all NWO grant applications and is not included in the page limit. In filling out this section, you may refer to other specific parts of the application for more detailed information compared to the information you provide here.

1. Will this project involve re-using existing research data?

Yes: Are there any constraints on its re-use?

No: Have you considered re-using existing data but discarded the possibility? Why?

If no, please briefly explain why; if yes, state any constraints on re-use of existing data if there are any.

As explained in section 5.1, the Macroscopic has a federated structure and data management is the responsibility of the data owners. The Macroscopic mandates that data is “as open as possible, as secure as necessary”. Therefore, some data owners place constraints (e.g. access via secure environment, non-commercial use allowed, etc) depending on the nature and sensitivity of the data they hold. The facilities in the Macroscopic Core make a significant contribution in enabling access to highly sensitive and therefore restricted access data.

2. Will data be collected or generated that are suitable for reuse?

Yes: Please answer questions 3 and 4.

No: Please explain why the research will not result in reusable data or in data that cannot be stored or data that for other reasons are not relevant for reuse.

3. After the project has been completed, how will the data be stored for the long-term and made available for the use by third parties? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons? Please state these here.

Data that is collected or generated within the Macroscopic must be made available “as open as possible, as secure as necessary” for research purposes to third parties. Therefore, data will be made freely available whenever possible, though constraints can be placed if the sensitivity of the data asks for it. In the latter case, access conditions will have to be clearly specified, in line with the requirements of the Data Access Broker (Task 1.1). Moreover, the Macroscopic user agreement stipulates that all data collected or generated within the project must be archived in a trusted repository within 6 months. The data owners are responsible for the choice of the specific repository, though the Senior Technical Lead and Technical Leads will provide advice and recommendations.

4. Will any costs (financial and time) related to data management and sharing/preservation be incurred?

Yes: Then please be sure to specify the associated expenses in the budget table of this application.

No: All the necessary resources (financial and time) to store and prepare data for sharing/preservation are or will be available at no extra cost.

8. Declarations and signature

Funding elsewhere

Have you requested funding via a grant application for this research infrastructure elsewhere?

- No
 Yes

Please include details of any additional grants you have requested for this LSRI project.

Ethical aspects

Check the relevant fields by adding an X. Note that ethical approval may also be required for research in non-medical contexts. If your grant application is successful, all applicable ethical approval documents will need to be sent to NWO before the start of the LSRI.

	Not applicable	Not yet applied for	Applied for	Received
Approval from a medical ethics review committee	x			
Approval from an animal experiments committee	x			
Permission for research with the population screening Act	x			
Approval from any other recognised ethics review committee(s)		x		

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I have completed this form truthfully;
- I satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2018](#);
- I have submitted non-referees (no more than 3 in total);
- I have entered all co-applicants in ISAAC;
- I endorse and follow the Code Openness Animal Experiments (if applicable);
- I endorse and follow the Code Biosecurity (if applicable);
- The consortium partners are aware of the NWO Grant Rules and obligatory establishment of an agreement containing IP&P arrangements and will adhere to this if the proposal is awarded.

Initial(s) and surname(s): Dr. Thomas Emery

Place: Rotterdam

Date: 23rd September 2024